

ALFRED-WEGENER-INSTITUT
HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FÜR POLAR-
UND MEERESFORSCHUNG

Frozen stocks and hidden fluxes: quantifying mercury release from coastal erosion along the Yukon coast, Canada

Master's Thesis

to attain the academic degree of
Master of Science (M.Sc.) in Geoecology

Submitted by

Katharina Jaspers

Institute of Environmental Sciences & Geography
University of Potsdam

1st supervisor: Dr. Michael Fritz

2nd supervisor: Dr. Anna Irrgang

Potsdam, August 18th, 2025

Katharina Jaspers

katharina.jaspers@uni-potsdam.de

Student number: 820421

1st reviewer

Dr. Michael Fritz

Telegrafenberg A45S

14473 Potsdam

michael.fritz@awi.de

2nd reviewer

Dr. Anna Irrgang

Telegrafenberg A45S

14473 Potsdam

anna.irrgang@awi.de

Abstract

Ongoing climate warming accelerates permafrost thaw and coastal erosion in the Arctic, mobilizing sediment-bound mercury (Hg) that was previously locked in frozen ground. Its neurotoxic and bioaccumulating form, methylmercury (MeHg), poses serious risks for ecosystems, marine biota, and Arctic Indigenous Peoples. To better understand this risk, this study aimed to quantify the present Hg stock in terrestrial sediments of the Yukon Coastal Plain (YCP), Canada, to estimate the annual Hg flux from coastal erosion, and to evaluate the likely fate of released Hg in the marine environment.

Hg concentrations were measured for 158 terrestrial and marine sediment samples. Based on previous studies, the YCP was divided into 44 terrain units, consisting of several uniform depth layers. Layer-specific Hg contents were upscaled from the concentrations measured in terrestrial samples of the respective terrain unit and layer. Where no measurement was available, the Hg concentration was predicted using a random forest model. Calculated stocks per terrain unit were combined with erosion rates to derive Hg fluxes. Marine sediment Hg concentrations and MeHg measurements provided insights into offshore transport and transformation pathways.

The total Hg stock of the YCP was estimated at 381,080 kg (271,540 to 501,930 kg), of which about 113 kg (87 to 163 kg) are released annually into the Beaufort Sea. Highest Hg stocks and fluxes occurred in high bluffs at Herschel Island–Qikiqtaruk (HIQ) and the eastern part of the mainland coast. Marine sediments exhibited generally lower Hg concentrations than terrestrial sediments, implying that a substantial fraction of the released Hg is transported offshore, re-emitted into the atmosphere, or incorporated into biogeochemical cycling in the nearshore zone. Sedimentary MeHg concentrations were low, but substantial methylation might occur in the water column, where it can effectively be taken up by phytoplankton, entering the Arctic food web. Since sediment data alone cannot resolve exposure risk, future work should target Hg speciation in water and key biota to understand risks for ecosystems and local communities.

Zusammenfassung

Die anhaltende Klimaerwärmung beschleunigt das Tauen von Permafrost und die damit einhergehende Küstenerosion in der Arktis. Sedimentgebundenes Quecksilber (Hg), das zuvor im gefrorenen Boden gespeichert war, wird damit mobilisiert. Seine neurotoxische und bioakkumulierende Form, Methylquecksilber (MeHg), stellt ein erhebliches Gesundheitsrisiko für Ökosysteme, marine Lebewesen und indigene Völker in der Arktis dar. Diese Studie zielte darauf ab, den Hg-Gehalt der terrestrischen Sedimente des Yukon Coastal Plain (YCP) in Nordwest-Kanada zu erfassen, jährliche Hg-Flüsse infolge der Küstenerosion abzuleiten, und nachzuvollziehen, wohin das freigesetzte Hg gelangt.

Hierfür wurden Hg-Konzentrationen in mehr als 200 terrestrischen und marinen Sedimentproben gemessen. Frühere Studien haben das YCP in 44 terrain units unterteilt, die jeweils aus mehreren homogenen Tiefenschichten bestehen. Diese Unterteilung wurde aufgegriffen und schichtspezifische Hg-Gehalte wurden aus den Messwerten abgeleitet. Für Schichten, in denen keine Messungen vorlagen, wurde die Hg-Konzentration mithilfe eines Random Forest-Modells vorhergesagt. Die berechneten Hg-Bestände pro terrain unit wurden mit Erosionsraten kombiniert, um jährliche Hg-Flüsse abzuleiten. Messungen von Hg- und MeHg-Konzentrationen in marinen Sedimenten lieferten Hinweise auf Hg-Transport ins offene Meer und auf Umwandlungsprozesse unter verschiedenen Umweltbedingungen.

Der Gesamt-Hg-Bestand des YCP wurde auf 381.080 kg (271.540 bis 501.930 kg) geschätzt, wovon jährlich etwa 113 kg (87 bis 163 kg) in die Beaufortsee freigesetzt werden. Die höchsten Hg-Bestände und -Flüsse traten in den steilen Kliffbereichen von Herschel Island–Qikiqtaruk sowie im östlichen Teil der Festlandküste auf. Die niedrigeren Hg-Konzentrationen in marinen Sedimenten im Vergleich zu terrestrischen Proben weisen auf einen substanziellen Transport des freigesetzten Hg ins offene Meer, eine Abgabe in die Atmosphäre oder eine Aufnahme in biogeochemische Kreisläufe der küstennahen Zone hin. Die niedrigen sedimentären MeHg-Konzentrationen lassen keine direkten Schlüsse auf Folgen für Ökosysteme und die lokale Bevölkerung zu. Hg könnte in erheblichem Umfang methyliert werden, von Phytoplankton aufgenommen werden und so ins marine arktische Nahrungsnetz gelangen. Weitere Studien sollten die Auswirkungen von

Hg im Wasser und in Schlüsselorganismen wie Phytoplankton oder marinen Säugetieren erforschen.

Table of content

Abstract.....	III
Zusammenfassung.....	IV
Table of content.....	VI
List of abbreviations.....	IX
List of figures.....	X
List of tables.....	XII
1 Introduction.....	1
2 Objectives.....	5
3 Scientific background.....	6
3.1 Permafrost and coastal dynamics in the Arctic.....	6
3.2 Contaminants in permafrost.....	8
3.3 Material fluxes from erosion of the Yukon coast.....	10
4 Study area.....	11
4.1 General setting.....	11
4.2 Climate and vegetation.....	12
4.3 Landscape evolution.....	13
4.4 Coastal dynamics.....	16
4.5 Sediment characteristics in the Canadian Beaufort Sea.....	17
5 Material and methods.....	19
5.1 Field work.....	19
5.1.1 Sampling strategy.....	19
5.1.2 Terrestrial samples.....	19
5.1.3 Marine sediment samples.....	21
5.2 Laboratory work.....	21
5.2.1 Sample preparation.....	21
5.2.2 Mercury, Carbon, and Nitrogen.....	22
5.2.3 Methylmercury.....	23

5.2.3.1	Extraction.....	23
5.2.3.2	Analysis.....	24
5.2.3.3	Processing.....	25
5.2.4	Grain size.....	26
5.3	Data analysis	27
5.3.1	Significance and correlation	27
5.3.2	Modeling mercury concentrations.....	28
5.3.2.1	Data preparation.....	28
5.3.2.2	Random forest model.....	28
5.3.2.3	Prediction and uncertainty	32
5.3.2.4	Simpler approaches.....	32
5.3.3	Estimating stocks & fluxes.....	32
6	Results	34
6.1	Geochemical parameters	34
6.1.1	Total mercury.....	34
6.1.2	Methylmercury.....	36
6.1.3	Carbon and nitrogen.....	38
6.1.4	Grain size distribution.....	42
6.2	Correlation matrices.....	44
6.2.1	Terrestrial samples.....	44
6.2.2	Marine samples	45
6.3	Mercury stocks & fluxes from the Yukon coast	46
6.3.1	Model evaluation	46
6.3.2	Predictions.....	49
6.3.3	Stocks.....	51
6.3.4	Fluxes	53
7	Discussion.....	58
7.1	Assessment of outcomes and uncertainties.....	58
7.1.1	Model behavior and performance.....	58
7.1.2	Evaluation and contextualization of mercury stocks and fluxes	61
7.2	Mercury in the terrestrial coastal domain	63
7.2.1	Terrestrial mercury concentrations in the Arctic context	63
7.2.2	Spatial variability of mercury stocks.....	64
7.2.3	Drivers of mercury fluxes from coastal erosion	66

7.3	Fate of mercury in the marine environment	67
7.4	Methylmercury—transformations, pathways, potential risk.....	69
7.4.1	Spatial patterns and environmental controls on methylmercury.....	69
7.4.2	Nearshore methylmercury dynamics	70
7.4.3	Potential risks and implications for Arctic food webs	72
7.5	Mercury in the One Health framework.....	73
8	Conclusion.....	76
9	References.....	78
	Appendix	XIII
	Acknowledgements	XVII
	Tools used in this thesis	XVIII
	Selbstständigkeitserklärung	XIX

List of abbreviations

C	carbon
CCME	Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment
DOM	Dissolved Organic Matter
g	gram
Hg	total mercury
HIQ	Herschel Island–Qikiqtaruk
ICP-MS	Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer
kg	kilogram
LIS	Laurentide Ice Sheet
M	molar
MeHg	methylmercury
µg	microgram
n	number of samples used
NaTeB	sodium tetraethyl-borate
OC	Organic Carbon
OM	Organic Matter
rpm	revolutions per minute
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
t	ton
Tg	teragram
TN	Total Nitrogen
TOC	Total Organic Carbon
WMAC-NS	Wildlife Management Advisory Council–North Slope
YC24	Yukon Coast 2024
YCP	Yukon Coastal Plain
yr	year

List of figures

Fig. 1.	Hg stocks in the Northern Hemisphere permafrost region	2
Fig. 2.	Characteristics of retrogressive thaw slumps	7
Fig. 3.	Location of the study area in northwestern Canada	12
Fig. 4.	Sample locations and types of the YC24 samples obtained during the YC24 expedition in July 2024	20
Fig. 5.	Workflow of sample analysis	22
Fig. 6.	Workflow of Hg modelling using a random forest model	31
Fig. 7.	Terrestrial sediment Hg concentrations across the longitudinal gradient of the YCP from west (W) to east (E)	34
Fig. 8.	Marine sediment Hg concentrations across the longitudinal gradient of the YCP from west (W) to east (E)	35
Fig. 9.	Terrestrial sediment MeHg concentrations from different parent material types and locations	37
Fig. 10.	Marine sediment MeHg concentrations from grab samples and short sediment cores along a 2000 m offshore transect from the southeast coast of HIQ in front of Slump D	37
Fig. 11.	Vertical distribution of Hg, MeHg, TOC, and TN in terrestrial sediments from active layer, permafrost, mud pools, stabilized zones, and thaw streams	39
Fig. 12.	TOC distribution across terrain units and layers of the YCP from west (W) to east (E)	40
Fig. 13.	Distribution of Hg, TOC, TN, C/N ratio, MeHg, and SSA in marine sediments along the transect in front of Slump D (n = 24)	42
Fig. 14.	Grain size distribution of YC24 samples of different types from Slump D, the mainland coast, and marine sediment samples	44
Fig. 15.	Correlation matrix of field and geochemical parameters in terrestrial sediment samples (n = 52)	45

Fig. 16.	Correlation matrix of field and geochemical parameters in marine sediment samples (n = 24).	46
Fig. 17.	Accuracy plot showing the relationship between actual and predicted Hg concentrations from the 158 training data points.	47
Fig. 18.	Importance assessment of the predictors used for the random forest model.	48
Fig. 19.	Predicted Hg concentrations for surface and deeper samples from the random forest model across the longitudinal gradient of the YCP from west (W) to east (E).	49
Fig. 20.	Average Hg concentrations per terrain unit and layer from measured and predicted data	50
Fig. 21.	Hg concentrations in the upper 1 m across the six lithologies of the YCP.	51
Fig. 22.	Hg stocks [g m^{-2}] of the Yukon coast.	52
Fig. 23.	Hg stocks [g m^{-3}] across the eight sections of the Yukon coast.	53
Fig. 24.	Hg fluxes [$\text{g m}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$] from the Yukon coast.	54
Fig. 25.	Hg fluxes [$\text{g m}^{-3} \text{yr}^{-1}$] across the eight sections of the Yukon coast.	55
Fig. 26.	The One Health framework in the Arctic.	74
Fig. 27.	MeHg extraction with two separate layers of two liquid mixtures.	XIII
Fig. 28.	Ice-wedge polygons (A) and thermokarst lakes (B) at the Yukon mainland coast, and coastal erosion at cliffs of HIQ (C).	XIV
Fig. 29.	Slump D on HIQ.	XV
Fig. 30.	Active layer detachments on HIQ.	XV
Fig. 31.	Grain size distribution for all YC24 samples.	XVI

List of tables

Tab. 1.	Classification of terrain units into eight sections and their characteristics.	15
Tab. 2.	Components added prior to MeHg analysis.	25
Tab. 3.	Random forest model predictors, their source, and how the data were prepared for the model.	29
Tab. 4.	Statistical results from Hg:TOC ratios.	48
Tab. 5.	Section allocation, characteristics, stocks, and fluxes per terrain unit. ...	56

1 Introduction

Changing climate is now visibly impacting ecosystems worldwide, with increasing air and water temperatures, more heavy precipitation events, and an increasing number of droughts (IPCC 2023). The Arctic is even more affected, as warming there is nearly four times as high as in the rest of the world (Rantanen et al. 2022). This has consequences for the entire Arctic system, with decreasing sea ice coverage and less perennial ice (Stroeve et al. 2012), impacts on marine ecosystems, and changing living conditions for people living in the Arctic (IPCC 2022). Another major consequence of the changing climate in the Arctic is the warming and thawing of permafrost (Biskaborn et al. 2019) which is ground that stays at or below 0 °C for at least two consecutive years (van Everdingen 1976). Among many others, thawing permafrost is of concern for two reasons:

(1) About 65 % of the Arctic coasts are unlithified, consisting of sediments that are freeze-bound (Lantuit et al. 2012). Rising air and water temperatures accelerate the degradation of these coasts, leading to an acceleration of coastal erosion and land loss (Lantuit et al. 2012; Irrgang et al. 2022).

(2) The Northern Hemisphere permafrost region stores $1,656 \pm 962$ Gg mercury (Hg), holding about twice as much Hg as held by the atmosphere, vegetation, and soils from non-permafrost regions together (Schuster et al. 2018). Mercury concentrations in permafrost soils have been found to be significantly higher than in soils from temperate regions (Olson et al. 2018), with large stocks in Russia and at the Canadian coast (Fig. 1). With thawing permafrost, a part of this large pool gets released into the environment (Dastoor et al. 2022). Once mobilized, Hg can follow various pathways: runoff and erosion may transport it into nearby surface and nearshore ocean waters, where it may be incorporated into riverine and coastal sediments, re-distributed with river flow and currents, or emitted into the atmosphere in gaseous form (Kirk et al. 2012; Dastoor et al. 2022). Seasonal environmental conditions, geomorphology, and the hydrologic regime are among the factors influencing the fate of released Hg in the environment (Dastoor et al. 2022).

Figure 1: Hg stocks in the Northern Hemisphere permafrost region (Westerveld et al. 2023).

Mercury is a naturally occurring element, primarily derived from geogenic sources and transported through the atmosphere. Once released from thawing permafrost, previously locked Hg becomes mobile and can influence the chemistry composition of ecosystems. The total Hg flux from coastal erosion into the Arctic Ocean has been estimated in different studies at 38,500 kg yr⁻¹ (AMAP 2021), 39,000 (18,000-52,000) kg yr⁻¹ (Dastoor et al. 2022), and 47,300 kg yr⁻¹ (Outridge et al. 2008). The released Hg can be transformed into methylmercury (MeHg), a toxic and bioavailable form of Hg. MeHg is a neurotoxic bioaccumulating pollutant, with negative and potentially irreversible effects on brain, nervous system, hormonal and enzymatic reactions (Clarkson 1992; Hong et al. 2012). It accumulates in aquatic food webs, posing serious risks to marine biota and humans (Mason et al. 1995; AMAP 2021). Top predators such as polar bears, belugas, and seabirds are especially affected due to their high ranking in the food web, as well as Arctic Indigenous Peoples who rely on traditional hunting and fishing for their diet and cultural identity (AMAP 2021).

Circum-Arctic estimates of Hg stocks and fluxes exist, but they come with high uncertainties (Schuster et al. 2018; Dastoor et al. 2022). Regional assessments are needed to better understand the underlying processes and local risks, particularly since permafrost coastal erosion rates and Hg stocks vary substantially with time and region (Hugues Lantuit et al. 2012; Schuster et al. 2018; Irrgang et al. 2022). Arctic Indigenous Peoples could benefit from more local approaches, which help to set the foundation for risk assessment associated with Hg in their respective region (Houde et al. 2022).

This study focuses on the Yukon Coastal Plain (YCP), a coastal lowland in northwestern Canada at the Beaufort coast. The area is characterized by high coastal erosion rates up to 22 m yr⁻¹ (Obu et al. 2017), and consequently high sediment and material fluxes (Couture et al. 2018). The YCP is part of the Ivvavik National Park of Canada, and the only island of the Yukon, Herschel Island–Qikiqtaruk (HIQ), became a Territorial Park in 1987 as a result of the Inuvialuit Final Agreement (IFA 1984). These protected areas are ecologically, economically, and culturally important (IFA 2005). To preserve and manage them, knowledge about Hg stocks and fluxes might be of relevance. With local communities relying on hunting and fishing, understanding the potential effects of Hg released from thawing permafrost is important for environmental stewardship and food safety. To date, only one study has estimated Hg fluxes from coastal erosion at the Canadian Beaufort coast: Leitch (2006) reported a maximum estimate of annual Hg fluxes of 165 kg from the Yukon mainland coast, and 85 kg from HIQ. Other research in the region has focused on stocks and fluxes of sediment, carbon (C), and nitrogen (Tanski et al. 2016; Couture et al. 2018; Tanski et al. 2019; Wagner et al. 2023; Wagner et al. 2025).

Limited information exists about Hg concentrations and MeHg biomagnification in the Beaufort Sea area. Over the last decades, increasing Hg concentrations have been detected in several marine fish, seabird, and mammal species (AMAP 2021). Ringed seals, belugas and polar bears in the Beaufort Sea region show higher Hg burdens than those in other parts of the Canadian Arctic, likely due to differing food web dynamics (AMAP 2021). While MeHg in soil usually makes up only a few percent of the total Hg pool, this value is at up to 99 % in fish and Beluga muscles (Loseto et al. 2008).

Previous studies indicate that substantial amounts of Hg are present at the YCP and in the Canadian Beaufort Sea, with recently increasing Hg concentrations in some marine biota (Leitch 2006; Kirk et al. 2012; Emmerton et al. 2013; Braune et al. 2015). The annual Hg contribution from the Mackenzie River was estimated to be more than three times higher than from coastal erosion (Leitch 2006). Still, it remains highly uncertain how much Hg is mobilized from coastal erosion, and what happens with it once it gets released. Despite the expected lower Hg contribution from coastal erosion compared to the one from the Mackenzie River, closing this knowledge gap is important, especially in areas where erosion is the dominant lateral material transport pathway and rivers are small or absent. Hg coming from coastal permafrost can have different chemical and physical characteristics than Hg coming from riverine sources, and might behave differently in marine environments (Du et al. 2024). For the Yukon coast, very few Hg measurements of terrestrial and marine sediments exist, and it is unclear whether Hg released from coastal erosion is of concern in this area and what happens with the released Hg entering the nearshore zone. If buried quickly in nearshore sea floor sediments, it may pose little risk to Arctic food webs. However, if transported and transformed into MeHg in the marine water column, or frequently remobilized in shallow water, it has the potential to affect Arctic ecosystems and human health through dietary exposure.

2 Objectives

The aim of this thesis is to quantify Hg stocks in terrestrial permafrost of the YCP and to estimate Hg fluxes resulting from coastal erosion. Additionally, this study discusses the potential fate of released Hg in the marine environment. To achieve this, Hg concentrations were measured in terrestrial and marine sediment samples, which were obtained during the Yukon Coast expedition (July 2024) and prior field campaigns. To scale up from point measurements to the landscape scale, the terrain segmentation approach from Couture et al. (2018) was used, which divided the YCP into 44 distinct terrain units, each characterized by relatively homogenous properties and depth-layers structures. For layers and terrain units where no measurements were available, a random forest model was applied to fill data gaps by predicting Hg concentrations based on other available environmental parameters. This allowed for the completion of the data set and enabled the calculation of Hg stocks for all terrain units. Estimated stocks were combined with coastal erosion rates to calculate annual Hg fluxes entering the nearshore zone. MeHg concentrations were measured for a certain sample set to gain insight into possible transformation processes and hotspots of methylation. The potential fate of released Hg was discussed based on marine sediment measurements and insights from the literature. Ultimately, this thesis aims to assess whether the released Hg is likely to be buried, transformed, or transported—and what implications this may have for ecosystems and humans.

3 Scientific background

3.1 Permafrost and coastal dynamics in the Arctic

Permafrost extends over about 15 % of the land masses of the Northern Hemisphere (Obu et al. 2019). In some locations, hundreds of meters thick deposits have accumulated over millennia (Alexeeva & Erbajeva 2000; Schirrmeister et al. 2002; French 2007). Low soil temperatures in permafrost regions strongly suppress microbial activity, limiting decomposition and mineralization of the organic material (OM) coming from flora and fauna. As a result, vast amounts of organic carbon (OC) have accumulated and been preserved in permafrost and the active layer (the layer on top of permafrost which is subject to annual freeze-thaw cycles) (Hugelius et al. 2014). With accelerated thawing of permafrost and melting of the contained ground ice, increasing quantities of this stored carbon are being mineralized and evade into the atmosphere as carbon dioxide or methane, two potent greenhouse gases (Schuur et al. 2015). This creates a self-reinforcing feedback loop, known as the permafrost carbon feedback, where warming accelerates emissions, which in turn intensify warming and further permafrost degradation (Friedlingstein et al. 2001; Schuur et al. 2015). The Arctic Ocean is currently acting as a carbon sink, estimated to sequester about 52 to 226 Tg carbon from atmospheric carbon dioxide annually (Vonk, Fritz et al. 2025). This capacity is increasingly offset by the release of terrestrial OC into the Arctic Ocean—estimated at 4.9-14 Tg yr⁻¹ from coastal erosion and 47.71 (18.5-127) Tg yr⁻¹ from rivers (Vonk, Fritz et al. 2025).

The majority of Arctic permafrost coasts is subject to coastal erosion (Irrgang et al. 2022). The combination of ongoing thermal denudation (erosion due to the influence of sensible heat, water, or solar radiation) and thermal abrasion (combined effect of mechanical and thermal energy of water; Aré 1988) leads to permafrost degradation and the formation of thermokarst features in coastal areas (Günther et al. 2013). One such landscape feature resulting from thermal denudation is called retrogressive thaw slump (RTS), a slope failure forming in hilly terrain due to thawing of ice-rich permafrost or melting of massive ground ice (Nesterova et al. 2024). It is characterized by an eroding and retreating headwall cutting into the undisturbed tundra (Fig. 2; Lantuit & Pollard 2005). The eroded

material often accumulates in front of the relatively steep headwall, where it forms mud pools together with water from melting ground ice (Nesterova et al. 2024). Usually there are one or more creeks, called thaw streams, through which water and sediments are transported from the mud pools into the ocean. Parts of the RTS floor can stabilize (temporarily) when no more ground ice is present or exposed to warmer air or solar irradiation (Nesterova et al. 2024). RTSs are known to free large amounts of sediment and organic matter (OM) (Weege 2016).

Figure 2: Characteristics of retrogressive thaw slumps (modified from Lantuit & Pollard 2005).

Permafrost thaw in coastal regions causes the release of sediments, carbon, nutrients (e.g., nitrogen, phosphorus; Reyes & Lougheed 2015; Hugelius et al. 2020; Vonk, Fritz et al. 2025; Wagner et al. 2025), ancient DNAs (Vorobyova et al. 1997), and contaminants (e.g., heavy metals, legacy pollutants; Schuster et al. 2018; Miner et al. 2021) into Arctic nearshore waters. The material input changes chemical and physical properties of the water column, contributing to ocean acidification (Semiletov et al. 2016) and influencing primary productivity (Juma et al. 2025). All these processes alter the ecosystem services that are provided by Arctic coasts, such as providing habitat for marine biota, and ground for housing, subsistence activities, and cultural heritage for Indigenous Peoples (Malinauskaite et al. 2019; Bringloe et al. 2022; Liew et al. 2022).

Future Arctic projections show an increase in coastal erosion rates from historical averages of $0.9 \pm 0.4 \text{ m yr}^{-1}$ (1850-1950) to $1.6 \pm 0.5 \text{ m yr}^{-1}$ (low-emission scenario) or

$2.6 \pm 0.8 \text{ m yr}^{-1}$ (high-emission scenario) by the end of the 21st century (Nielsen et al. 2022). This will set an increasing number of coastal communities and settlements at risk, potentially requiring relocation and increasing social, economic, and psychological costs, including food security and infrastructure loss (IPCC 2022).

3.2 Contaminants in permafrost

Permafrost soils have accumulated not only large amounts of OM, but also of heavy metals (Perryman et al. 2020). Very little is known about the total stocks of heavy metals in permafrost. Recent studies have looked at arsenic, cadmium, chromium, cobalt, copper, manganese, mercury, nickel, lead, and zinc, among others (Ji et al. 2020; Perryman et al. 2020). Concentrations of these elements have been found to be elevated in some permafrost soils compared to soils of lower latitudes (Perryman et al. 2020; Miner et al. 2021). Even if concentrations would be low, the total amount in the large permafrost domain could have the potential to significantly set ecosystems at risk of pollution, when released at high rates.

This study focuses on Hg, a heavy metal with high density, high thermal and electrical conductivity, and low solubility in water. Hg in the environment occurs predominantly as elemental mercury Hg(0), oxidized mercury Hg(II), and methylmercury MeHg (CH_3Hg^+). Elemental Hg is liquid under standard conditions and is the dominant form of gaseous Hg in the atmosphere from volcanic activities (Siegel & Siegel 1984) and rock weathering (Wen et al. 2021). Natural emissions are increased by one-third from anthropogenic emissions, including coal combustion, artisanal and small-scale gold mining, and cement and metal production (UNEP 2013; Outridge et al. 2018). Dastoor et al. (2022) estimated that more than 98 % of the total Hg emissions occur in regions other than the Arctic but can be transported into the Arctic. In the atmosphere, Hg(0) has a residence time of about one year, allowing for long-range transport away from local sources and into remote regions such as the Arctic (Lindqvist & Rodhe 1985; Travnikov 2005).

The major deposition pathway of atmospheric Hg(0) into terrestrial systems in the Arctic tundra has been found to be the uptake by vegetation (Jiskra et al. 2019). Due to elevated Hg concentrations in the atmosphere since the beginning of the 20th century, Hg concentrations are often higher in the upper active layer than in the

underlying permafrost (Olson et al. 2018; Lim et al. 2020). In terrestrial reservoirs and natural waters, Hg(II) is the predominant form of Hg (Skylberg 2012). This oxidized Hg shows a high affinity for dissolved organic matter (DOM), particles, and sulfur (Skylberg 2012). Under anoxic conditions and the presence of microorganisms that carry the *hgcAB* gene pair (sulfate reducing bacteria, iron reducing bacteria, methanogens, among others), Hg(II) can be transformed into MeHg, a neurotoxic compound that bioaccumulates in food webs, with increasing concentrations towards higher trophic levels (Jonsson et al. 2022). MeHg production in Arctic soils is generally limited by cold temperatures and low microbial activity (Yang et al. 2016; Tarbier et al. 2021), and MeHg concentrations in permafrost soils usually make up for only a small fraction (less than 5 %) of total Hg (Olson et al. 2018; Tarbier et al. 2021).

Hg stored in Arctic soils can be mobilized and transported into aquatic (terrestrial and marine) systems via riverine transport and coastal erosion (Dastoor et al. 2022). Arctic rivers drain large catchments underlain by permafrost, and deliver Hg bound to DOM and mineral particles into the Arctic Ocean (Schuster et al. 2011), predominantly in the form of Hg(II) (Dastoor et al. 2022). Riverine inputs peak in spring and early summer, when 90 % of the total annual Hg flux coming with Arctic rivers is exported into the oceans (Zolkos et al. 2020). Coastal erosion releases Hg that has been previously locked in frozen sediments directly into the nearshore marine environment. This process primarily introduces particulate-bound Hg(II), often associated with clay surfaces and OM (Brigatti et al. 2005; Rutkowski et al. 2021). Since a lot of this material is derived from deeper (older) sediments, it may contain Hg that has been isolated from biogeochemical cycling for centuries or millennia (Rutkowski et al. 2021).

In marine waters, the released Hg(II) can be deposited and buried on the sea floor (particle-bound Hg), where it may remain relatively stable (Braune et al. 2015). Some fractions of Hg(II) can be transformed into MeHg by microbial communities in sediments or in the water column (Jonsson et al. 2022). MeHg production has been observed in Arctic marine environments, especially in shelf seas where terrestrial inputs are high and primary productivity supports microbial activity (Chételat et al. 2022; Jonsson et al. 2022). MeHg produced in the ocean can be demethylated by photo-reduction or biotic demethylation to Hg(0) and can evade back into the atmosphere (Driscoll et al. 2013; Dastoor et al. 2022). Another fraction can enter the

base of the marine food web via uptake by phytoplankton and microbes (Watras et al. 1998; Braune et al. 2015). It then biomagnifies through trophic levels, resulting in elevated concentrations in fish, seabirds, and marine mammals, posing risks to both wildlife and Indigenous Peoples that rely on traditional diets (Loseto et al. 2008; AMAP 2021).

3.3 Material fluxes from erosion of the Yukon coast

The Yukon coast is characterized by high rates of coastal erosion (Obu et al. 2017; Irrgang et al. 2018). Along the approximately 300 km long coastline, more than 200,000 m² land are lost each year, releasing about 1.83×10^6 m³ of sediment into the Arctic Ocean (Couture et al. 2018). This annually released sediment is estimated to contain about 35.5×10^6 kg of carbon (Couture et al. 2018). The Hg flux from the Yukon coast has been estimated by Leitch (2006) at approximately 250 kg. These fluxes make the Yukon coast a large contributor of permafrost-derived material entering the Arctic marine environment. The consequences of this release with all its components (carbon, nutrients, contaminants, microbes) are only partially understood.

For the Inuvialuit and Gwich'in communities living in this region, subsistence harvesting of marine mammals, fish, and seabirds make up an important part of their diet and culture (Donaldson et al. 2010; AMAP 2015). Because these marine biota rank high in the food web, they can accumulate high levels of MeHg through biomagnification, potentially posing health risks to the people consuming large amounts of such organisms (Dietz et al. 2013). Understanding the sources and pathways of Hg is therefore critical for risk assessments and the development of effective protection and management strategies for both ecosystems and Indigenous Peoples (Grandjean et al. 2010).

4 Study area

4.1 General setting

The YCP in the northwest of Canada is a 10 to 40 km wide lowland that gently slopes northward towards the Beaufort Sea (Welsh & Rigby 1971). It is bordered by the Arctic Coastal Plain of Alaska in the west and extends eastward to the Mackenzie Delta. To the south, the YCP is framed by the British, Barn and Richardson mountains (Welsh & Rigby 1971). The island HIQ is part of the YCP and lies approximately 3 km off the Yukon mainland coast on the Canadian Beaufort Sea shelf (Fig. 3). The island covers an area of about 116 km² and rises to a maximum elevation of 181 m above sea level. Once connected to the mainland, HIQ became an island within the last 1600 years (Burn 2009). Today, the very shallow Workboat Passage separates it from the Yukon mainland coast. When referring to YCP and the Yukon coast in this thesis, HIQ is always included.

In 1987, HIQ was designated as a Territorial Park under the Inuvialuit Final Agreement (1984) and the Government of Yukon's *Parks Act* with the aim to “protect and sustain the ecological integrity and heritage values for generations to come” (WMAC-NS 2019) and to conserve wildlife, habitat and traditional indigenous use (IFA 1984). At the same time, the Ivvavik National Park of Canada was established, followed recently by the Aullaviat/Anguniarvik Traditional Conservation Area (2023), which together encompass large parts of northwest Canada, including the entire YCP (Government of Canada 2025).

The YCP borders the Canadian Beaufort Sea, which is a marginal sea of the Arctic Ocean. Its shallow parts form the Canadian Beaufort Sea shelf with an approximate width of 150 km and up to 80 m water depth (Hill et al. 1991). The Mackenzie Trough (northeast of HIQ) and Herschel Basin (southeast of HIQ) are the only deeper parts of the shelf. Further offshore, the Canadian Beaufort Sea shelf slopes into the adjacent Beaufort Basin which reaches depths greater than 3600 m (Lemenkova 2020). The entire region lies in the continuous permafrost zone (permafrost coverage > 90 %; Obu et al. 2019), and parts of the shelf area are underlain by subsea permafrost (Overduin et al. 2019).

Figure 3: Location of the study area in northwestern Canada. The Yukon coast is divided into 44 terrain units (Couture et al. 2018), which are classified into 8 sections in this study, based on characteristics of the respective terrain units (Tab.1). The limit of the Last Glacial Maximum is taken from Ehlers et al. (2011).

4.2 Climate and vegetation

The climate at the Yukon coast is characterized by continental Arctic air masses during the long, cold winters, and maritime Arctic air during the short, cool summers (Rampton 1982). From 1991 to 2020, the average temperature was $-24\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in February and $8.2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in July at the Komakuk Beach weather station (Environment & Climate Change Canada (ECCC) 2025). Compared to the previous period from 1961 to 1990, this represents an increase of $2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in February and $0.6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in July (ECCC 2025). Rising air temperatures have been confirmed on HIQ, where Burn & Zhang (2009) reported a $2.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ rise in mean annual temperature over the 20th century. This local increase is assumed to reflect a broader regional trend beyond the Yukon coast (Burn & Zhang 2009). During the 20th century, mean annual ground temperatures rose both at the top of permafrost and at 20 m depth by $2.6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $1.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$,

respectively (Burn & Zhang 2009). The most recent precipitation data from ECCC are available for the period 1971 to 2000, showing a total precipitation of 161.3 mm yr⁻¹ for Komakuk Beach, of which 83.5 mm was rain (ECCC 2025). The two major wind directions along the Yukon coast are northwest and east (Radosavljevic et al. 2022; Brembach et al. 2023).

The YCP lies approximately 100 km north of the tree line, with Arctic Tundra as the main vegetation type (Scudder 1997). The region is primarily covered by tussock tundra with cotton grass (*Eriophorum* spp.) as the dominant vegetation type (Raynolds & Walker 2022). Other common plant types include dwarf shrubs, sedges, grasses, mosses, and lichens (Raynolds & Walker 2022). The vegetation communities vary locally and are strongly influenced by local water regime and microtopography (Wolter et al. 2016). An increase in the abundance and extent of shrubs in tundra areas has been reported for large parts of the Arctic (Tape et al. 2006; Mekonnen et al. 2021) and is expected for the YCP as well (Wolter et al. 2016).

4.3 Landscape evolution

The YCP is primarily composed of Pleistocene sediments, which are overlain by a layer of unconsolidated Holocene deposits that vary in thickness (up to > 15 m) and extend into the Beaufort Sea shelf (Rampton 1982; Fritz et al. 2012). The region's geology is strongly affected by its location at the interface of the unglaciated Beringian landscape to the west and the coverage by the Laurentide Ice Sheet (LIS) to the east (Rampton 1982; Fritz et al. 2012). During the Late Wisconsinan, between approximately 23,000 and 18,000 years ago, the LIS reached its maximum extent (Fig. 3; Rampton 1982). While areas west of Firth River, such as Komakuk Beach, remained ice-free, the ice sheet's influence is still visible in landscape features such as morainic ridges, kame terraces, and meltwater channels in the eastern region (Rampton 1982; Fritz et al. 2012).

HIQ itself was formed by the LIS, which pushed material from the adjacent Herschel Basin (Mackay 1959; Fritz et al. 2012). This is evident today from the presence of ice-thrust terrestrial and marine sediments on the island (Fritz et al. 2011; Fritz et al. 2012). As the ice sheet retreated and the Holocene began, rising summer temperatures triggered permafrost thawing, leading to the truncation of late

Pleistocene ice wedges and the incorporation of organic material into the soil (Fritz et al. 2012). A cooling climate in the middle Holocene caused the permafrost table to rise again, which reduced peat accumulation and promoted the growth of ice wedges again (Fritz et al. 2012). Fluctuations in sea levels during the Holocene had a strong impact on the deposition of coastal sediments through winnowing and transport by wave energy (Rampton 1982; Anthony 1989).

Today, alluvial fans and periglacial terraces are dominating the unglaciated regions of the YCP, with surficial sediments mostly of lacustrine or fluvial origin (Rampton 1982). The once glaciated areas show rolling to hummocky moraines, ice-thrust ridges, and meltwater channels, all indicating the previous presence of the LIS (Mackay 1959; Rampton 1982). Other landscape features of the YCP include steep and high cliffs, often with colluvial material in front, incising streams with terraces and flood plains, deltas of varying size, thick organic blankets cover (Welsh & Rigby 1971; Rampton 1982; Couture et al. 2018). Beaches of varying width can be found along most parts of the Yukon coast but are absent where thermal niching and block failures occur (Rampton 1982). About 45 % of the total volume of the YCP are made up of ground ice, with fine pore ice and segregated ice lenses as well as large ice bodies such as buried glacial ice and wedge ice (Rampton 1982; Couture et al. 2018; Wetterich et al. 2023).

Couture et al. (2018) divided the Yukon coast into 44 terrain units extending 2 km inland, with similar characteristics of the terrain units in “landforms, surficial material, permafrost conditions, and coastal processes” (Fig 3). Their segmentation was adopted for this study. Considering Quaternary geology (Rampton 1982), land cover (Bartsch et al. 2019), sediment description (Manson et al. 2019), bluff heights and ice volumes (Couture et al. 2018), and descriptions from Scudder (1997), terrain units with similar properties were summarized into eight sections for later comparisons (Fig. 3). A more detailed description of terrain units and sections can be found in Table 1.

Table 1: Classification of terrain units into eight sections and their characteristics. Eight sections were determined. Cliff height and erosion rate are taken from (Couture et al. 2018).

Section	Terrain units	Cliff height [m]	Erosion rate [m yr⁻¹]	Characteristics
1	Clarence Lagoon (W, E) Komakuk Beach (W1, W2) Malcolm River fan (with barrier island)	1 to 7.1	Around 1	Remained unglaciated; underlain by thick, unconsolidated marine and deltaic sediments; large alluvial fans and lacustrine plains; almost flat, incised by streams and rivers; more than 50 % ice content in the higher cliffs; varying ice content between 0 and 89 %
2	Nunaluk Spit Avadlek Spit Simpson Point Catton Point Whale Bay Stokes Point Phillips Bay W Kay Point Spit King Point Lagoon	Around 1	Up to 3.6 at Stokes Point and 1.2 at Nunaluk Spit, but mostly around 0.5	Marine beaches and spits of the YCP; stratified silt, sand, clay, and gravel, generally sand and gravel and some thick unconsolidated tills; no ground ice; remained mostly unglaciated or formed after glaciation
3	Herschel Island W, N, E, S Kay Point SE	Up to 36	Around 1 (Herschel Island N & W); around 0.3 (rest)	Ice-thrust moraine ridges; thick and continuous till; high ice volumes mostly > 30 %, up to 94 %, massive and excess ice are mostly present; glacially reworked
4	Workboat Passage W, E Whale Bay W, E Roland Bay NW	1.7 to 8.2	Up to 1, mostly around 0.3	Region of the limit of glaciation by the LIS; glacial outwash and rolling moraines; high ice volumes between 20 and 83 % with excess ice; sand and gravel
5	Roland Bay W, E Stokes Point W, SE Phillips Bay (NW)	4.7 to 13.8	0.4 to 0.9	Lacustrine deposits and rolling moraines; thick and continuous till with marine beaches at Roland Bay and Stokes Point; ice content between 20 and up to 87 %, massive ice at the rolling moraine deposits

6	Babbage River Delta	3.2	1	Large delta forming a fluvial flood plain; stratified silt, clay, sand, and gravel; no ground ice
7	Kay Point	3.2	1	Glacial outwash fan; stratified silt, clay, sand, and gravel; lower ice volume between 0 and 37 %
8	King Point (NW, SE) Sabine Point (W, E) Shingle Point W, E Running River	7.4 to 32.7 m	0.2 to 1.1	Lacustrine plain and rolling moraine deposits; thick and continuous till; varying ice volume mostly from 20 to 30 %, up to 97 %

Signs of thermokarst and thawing permafrost are obvious in most parts of the YCP in the form of ice-wedge polygons, thermokarst lakes and coastal erosion (Appendix, Fig. 28). With a density of 1.2 RTSs per kilometer of coast, the Yukon coast is highly affected by slumping, particularly east of HIQ (Ramage et al. 2017). The number of RTSs on HIQ has doubled between 1952 and 2000 with a total of 164 RTSs in 2000 (Lantuit & Pollard 2008). The island's largest RTS 'Slump D' is located at the southeastern coast (Fig. 4; Appendix, Fig. 29) During the 2024 expedition, many active layer detachments have been observed on HIQ from the helicopter (Appendix, Fig. 30).

4.4 Coastal dynamics

Coastal erosion is a major concern in the study area, significantly impacting both the coastline's structure and morphology. The unlithified coast is primarily held together by permafrost and low soil temperatures but increasing air and water temperatures, strong wave action, and relative sea level rise are exacerbating the erosion process (Fritz et al. 2017). On the Yukon coast, erosion rates average 1.3 m yr⁻¹ (Irrgang et al. 2018) with some locations experiencing rates as high as 22 m yr⁻¹ (Obu et al. 2017). On HIQ, the erosion rate varies between 0.3 and 1.2 m yr⁻¹ (Couture et al. 2018).

Strong storm events are among the main drivers of coastal erosion (Irrgang et al. 2022), causing high-intensity wave events which can contribute significantly to the annual erosion rates (Obu et al. 2017; Irrgang et al. 2022). During the open water season, when storm frequency increases and peaks in September and October, extreme winds (recorded at speeds of up to 23.3 m s^{-1} from the northwest and 14.7 m s^{-1} from the east; Radosavljevic et al. 2022) enhance wave action, promote wave overtopping, and accelerate the erosion processes (Atkinson 2005; Irrgang et al. 2022; Jones et al. 2025).

In addition to storm-driven impacts, the local hydrographic setting plays a significant role. The YCP lies in the microtidal zone, where astronomical tides rarely exceed 0.5 m (Harper 1990). Given this low tidal range, tides seem to have a negligible contribution to coastal erosion. Instead, winds, sea ice, and fluctuations in air pressure drive a large portion of the observed variability in water levels (Manson & Solomon 2007; Fukumori et al. 2021). This effect is further amplified by a rising sea level of 1.9 to 3.5 mm yr^{-1} in the Canadian Beaufort Sea (Manson et al. 2005; Han et al. 2015). Projections under a medium-emission scenario indicate that by 2100, sea levels could rise by an additional 0.7 to 0.76 m, further intensifying the erosion processes (Manson & Solomon 2007; Han et al. 2015).

Seasonality also moderates the erosive forces on the coast. The presence of sea ice, and especially landfast ice, which covers the Canadian Beaufort Sea and its shores from early October through the end of June (National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC) 2025), acts as a natural barrier that limits wave action and the ocean-atmosphere exchange (Jones et al. 2025; Vonk, Fritz et al. 2025). During the ice break-up period, easterly winds help push the ice away from the shore, allowing for increased wave activity and erosion (Falardeau et al. 2023).

4.5 Sediment characteristics in the Canadian Beaufort Sea

While coastal erosion is a significant source of sediment (Stein & MacDonald 2004; Wegner et al. 2015), the contribution from fluvial systems must not be overlooked. Several small rivers from the YCP such as Firth River, Malcolm River, and Roland Creek, release freshwater and sediments into the Canadian Beaufort Sea. These contributions are minor when compared with the vast sediment load delivered by

the Mackenzie River. Accounting for approximately 95 % of the total sediment supply of the Canadian Beaufort Sea (Hill et al. 1991), the Mackenzie River annually releases an estimated 124×10^6 t of sediments annually into the Arctic Ocean, making it the largest sediment source of all Arctic rivers (Holmes et al. 2002). The movement of its large sediment plume is strongly controlled by the volume of exported water, ocean currents, and wind strength and direction (Mulligan & Perrie 2019; Juhls et al. 2022) though in some coastal areas, particularly near the Herschel Basin, local rivers may exert a more dominant influence (Falardeau et al. 2023).

Once eroded, the fate of these sediments depends on their characteristics and the prevailing marine processes. Sea floor sediments of the Canadian Beaufort Sea shelf are predominantly composed of clay with interspersed silty and sandy patches (Pelletier 1984). An up to 35 m thick layer has been deposited here throughout the Holocene (Pelletier 1984). Fine-grained sediments eroded from the permafrost coast tend to be transported offshore, while coarser fractions (gravel and sand) accumulate and are transported along the shore, forming protective beaches and spits in several locations (McDonald & Lewis 1973).

The regional current systems play an essential role in redistributing sediments within the Canadian Beaufort Sea (Pelletier 1984). The Beaufort Gyre, a wind-driven and clockwise-rotating system, generates a westward surface current offshore (Timmermans & Toole 2023). Simultaneously, the Alaskan Coastal Current transports material eastward through the Workboat Passage close to shore. This direction is supported by the Beaufort Undercurrent (Aagaard 1984; Pickart 2004). No permanent settlements exist along the Yukon coast but many cultural features (including burial sites, single cabins, tent structures, or ice houses) represent the traditional importance of the coast (Irrgang et al. 2019). Camp sites such as Tapqaq (Shingle Point) are central for the local people's cultural identity and are the location for conducting traditional lifestyles such as summer games, fishing and whale hunting (IFA 2005; Turner & Lantz 2018). HIQ represents an important stop-over point for local and regional travelers during hunting and fishing trips and for knowledge transfer to younger generations (WMAC-NS 2019).

5 Material and methods

5.1 Field work

5.1.1 Sampling strategy

Field samples were taken during the Yukon Coast 2024 (YC24) expedition in July 2024. Terrestrial sediment samples from HIQ and the mainland coast were collected from active layers, permafrost cliffs, and the floor of Slump D. Additionally, marine sediments of a transect perpendicular to the coastline of Slump D was sampled. All samples were either kept frozen or were frozen as soon as possible after collection. They were stored in dark, air-free conditions as well as possible until further analysis. Whenever possible, samples were taken with a known volume to determine dry bulk density (DBD).

5.1.2 Terrestrial samples

Terrestrial sediment samples were taken in different ways using a corer, sample rings, an axe, or plastic bottles, and from different landscape types such as active layer, permafrost, mud pools, stabilized zones, and thaw streams. All samples were stored and transported in Whirl-Paks[®]. Two permafrost cores were extracted from undisturbed tundra on top of Slump D using a STIHL engine with a SIPRE corer (80 mm diameter). The cores were split according to changes in the sediment structure, natural breakages, transport suitability, or the boundary of the active layer. At the first location, about 3 m inland from the headwall, an ice wedge was hit, resulting in a short core with a total length of 52 cm. A second site was chosen about 20 m inland from the headwall, where a core with a total length of 138 cm was obtained. More permafrost samples were collected from natural exposures: using an axe and a hammer to extract the frozen material, samples from two vertical profiles from the headwall at Slump D and a bluff at the mainland coast were collected. Since these samples were manually extracted, they were non-volumetric. Undisturbed active layer samples were collected from both exposure sites, as well as from two additional locations at the mainland coast, using sample rings at various depths within the active layer. This method resulted in volumetric

samples. The same approach was used for obtaining samples from mud pools and stabilized zones in Slump D. Seven mud pool samples were collected from four sites in Slump D, including surface samples and samples from 20 cm below surface, along with two surface mud pool samples from the mainland coast. From stabilized zones in Slump D—characterized by very dry and partly vegetated areas—six samples were collected from three sites, again from both the surface and 20 cm depth. Finally, samples from sediments transported with three thaw streams in Slump D were collected by holding plastic bottles directly into the flowing water. Those samples (from mud pools, stabilized zones, and thaw streams) are sometimes referred to as “disturbed active layer” samples. The sampling locations are depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Sample locations and types of the YC24 samples obtained during the YC24 expedition in July 2024. The images show typical examples of the respective type, and the sampling strategy. Photos by AWI/Esther Horvath (coring) and Katharina Jaspers (all others).

5.1.3 Marine sediment samples

All YC24 marine sediment samples were collected along a transect starting at the outflow of Slump D and extending perpendicularly to the coastline. Two samples from 0 and 15 cm depth below surface were taken from the beach at Slump D (i.e., with 0 m distance to shore). From there, samples were taken every 100 m during the first kilometer and every 500 m during the second kilometer of the transect, resulting in 12 additional sampling sites. At seven of these sites, a van Veen grab sampler was used to obtain surface sediment samples. Using a spoon, the marine material was transferred into Whirl-Paks[®]. At three of these locations, a sample ring was taken from the material in the grabber to determine DBD, assuming the sample remained undisturbed during collection. At the other five locations, an UWITEC gravity corer with an inner diameter of 60 mm was used to gain sediment material. The corer, which sinks into the sediment by its own weight, contained liners that were closed and stored under a dark cover after retrieval. Back on the island, the cores were split into 0-2 cm (surface), 2-7 cm, and the deeper segments. The sample material was then transferred into Whirl-Paks[®]. In total, 24 marine sediment samples were collected, of which 20 were volumetric.

5.2 Laboratory work

5.2.1 Sample preparation

All analyses were conducted at the Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research in Potsdam, Germany (AWI). Only the MeHg measurements were carried out at the University of Stockholm, Sweden (Fig. 5). Back from field work, all 76 frozen samples were freeze-dried with a temperature of 35 °C at the heating plates. This temperature was selected to minimize the risk of MeHg degradation during the drying process. For freeze-drying, the sample bags were opened, covered with a cloth, and placed in the freeze-dryer until they were dry, which took between two to four days per run. Samples were weighed before and after drying to determine DBD for volumetric samples. After drying, the samples were split into three subsamples (Fig. 5). One subsample was grinded for Hg, Total Organic Carbon (TOC), Total Inorganic Carbon (TIC), and Total Nitrogen (TN) analyses using a planetary mill. Another subsample was grinded for MeHg

analysis using a coffee grinder to allow for better temperature control. The remaining subsample was left unprocessed for grain size analysis. Unless otherwise stated, all concentrations are reported as per dry weight and data are reported as mean \pm standard deviation.

Figure 5: Workflow of sample analysis. Samples were taken at the YCP, transported frozen to AWI Potsdam, and analyzed for Hg, TOC/TIC, TN, grain size distribution and MeHg (at University (U) of Stockholm).

5.2.2 Mercury, Carbon, and Nitrogen

Hg, TOC, TIC, and TN concentrations were analyzed by weighing in 50 mg of the milled samples. Several standards were analyzed along with the samples for quality control. Duplicate measurements were performed for each sample, and when the

relative standard deviation of the duplicates exceeded 5 %, an additional two 50 mg subsamples were analyzed. Hg concentrations were determined using a Milestone Direct Mercury Analysis System (DMA-80 evo, MWS-GmbH). TOC and TIC were measured with an ELEMENTAR soli TOC cube, and TN concentrations were obtained using an ELEMENTAR rapid MAX N exceed. The atomic C/N ratio was calculated using Equation (1):

$$C/N \text{ ratio} = \frac{TOC}{TN} \times 1.167. \quad (1)$$

5.2.3 Methylmercury

The process of MeHg determination can be divided into the extraction procedure (extracting MeHg from the sediment) and the actual analysis (measuring MeHg concentrations). The extraction and measurements were conducted at the University of Stockholm with a total of three days of extraction and four days of analysis.

5.2.3.1 Extraction

About 0.5 g of the grinded sample material was weighed in into new 50 ml Falcon tubes, along with three times 0.05 g of Certified Reference Material (CRM, MeHg concentration according to manufacturer: $75 \pm 4 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) for each of the four analysis days. Additionally, three empty Falcon tubes (blanks) were measured alongside the samples per analysis day to monitor potential contamination and background levels. An internal standard (IS; isotopically enriched Me^{200}Hg standard) was added to each tube: for samples and blanks, this was 100 μl of IS with a Me^{200}Hg concentration of 1.3 ppb (first day) / 1 ppb (all other days), and for the CRMs, this was 250 μl of IS with a Me^{200}Hg concentration of 13.9 ppb. Milli-Q® water was added, and the tubes were shaken to ensure that all sample particles were in contact with the liquid. Then, the tubes were left to equilibrate for one hour. The chemical extraction was initiated by adding 10 ml KBr (1.4 KBr in 10 % H_2SO_4), 2 ml CuSO_4 (1 M CuSO_4 in 250 ml), and 10 ml DCM (Dichloromethane CH_2Cl_2). The tubes were left to react for 45 minutes. They were then placed on a sample rotor (Fisherbrand™ Multi-Purpose

Tube Rotator) for 45 minutes at 65 rpm, followed by centrifugation at 3000 rpm for 5 minutes. This resulted in a separation of two liquid mixtures: a lower clear layer containing DCM and the extracted MeHg, and an upper greenish layer containing KBr and CuSO₄ (Appendix, Fig. 27). The lower layer was transferred into new Falcon tubes using glass Pasteur pipettes. To remove DCM from the extracted MeHg, 10 ml of Milli-Q® water were added to the tubes containing the pipetted liquid, which were placed in a warm water bath at 40 °C and purged from the DCM with nitrogen gas (N₂). This process evaporated the DCM, trapping the extracted MeHg in the Milli-Q® water. The tubes were stored in a freezer until analysis, which took place between one and five days later.

5.2.3.2 Analysis

MeHg content was measured with a Tekran® Model 2700 Methyl Mercury Analyzer connected to an Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer, thermo scientific iCAP TQ (ICP-MS). For analysis, samples, blanks, and CRMs were acidified by adding 225 µl acetate buffer (4 molar (M) solution; 2 M of sodium acetate and 2 M of glacial acetic acid dissolved in Milli-Q® water, final volume brought to 1 l) and ethylated adding 1 % sodium tetraethyl-borate (NaTeB). Calibration blanks and standards were created according to Table 2. All mixtures were prepared in brown glass vials, which were closed immediately after adding NaTeB to prevent MeHg loss due to evaporation. The samples were gently shaken and placed in the Tekran® analyzer, connected to the ICP-MS, for measurement.

Table 2: Components added prior to MeHg analysis. All numbers are given in ml. The working solutions Std10ppt and Std500ppt are MeHg standard diluted 20 times (Std10ppt) and 1000x (Std500ppt) with Milli-Q® water, glacial acetic acid, and HCl.

Label	Milli-Q® water	Acetate buffer	Std10ppt	Std500ppt	IS	sample	NaTeB
Milli-Q® water	30						
Calblank (3x)	29.745	0.225					0.03
Std0.02	29.685	0.225	0.06				0.03
Std0.05	29.595	0.225	0.15				0.03
Std0.1 (3x)	29.445	0.225	0.30				0.03
Std0.5	29.715	0.225		0.03			0.03
Std2	29.625	0.225		0.12			0.03
Std4	29.505	0.225		0.24			0.03
Samples & blanks	27.745	0.225				2.0	0.03
CRM (3x)	29.645	0.225				0.1	0.03
Calblank + IS (3x)	29.705	0.225			0.04		0.03
Std2 + IS (3x)	29.585	0.225		0.12	0.04		0.03

5.2.3.3 Processing

The results from the Tekran® analyzer were used for external calibration to verify the concentration of the standards. From the data from the ICP-MS, the abundances of the different Hg isotopes in the IS were calculated. By considering the ratios of Me²⁰⁰Hg and Me²⁰²Hg in both the IS and the natural environment, the ICP-MS signals were deconvoluted to distinguish between naturally occurring and spiked mercury isotopes. Using the known volume and concentration of the IS, the mass of Me²⁰⁰Hg per ICP-MS count was determined. This ratio was then applied to calculate the concentration of MeHg per sample. To assess precision, triplicate analyses were performed for four selected samples representing high and low TOC content as well as high and low Hg concentrations. Deviations between the triplicates ranged from 6.2 to 41.3 % (relative standard deviation). The

concentrations of the blanks were below 0.001 ng g^{-1} . The CRMs showed a mean concentration of $76.9 \pm 3.6 \text{ ng g}^{-1}$.

5.2.4 Grain size

Prior to grain size analysis, the sample material was treated to maintain only mineral components by removing all organic material. For this, 100 ml of 3 % H_2O_2 and 2-3 drops of ammonia (NH_3) were added to 7-10 g of freeze-dried sample material. The samples were shaken for 15 minutes each day on a plate shaker, and every one to two days, 10 ml of 30 % H_2O_2 was added. The pH value was monitored and maintained between 6.5 and 8 by adding either acetic acid (CH_3COOH) or NH_3 as needed. Once the pH value remained stable for several days and the liquid above the dispersed sediment appeared clear, the excess liquid was removed by centrifuging and decanting. The samples were then frozen and freeze-dried with $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at the heating plates. Approximately 1.6 to 5.2 g of dried material was weighed in into plastic bottles, tetrasodium pyrophosphate was added, and the bottles were filled with Milli-Q[®] water. They were placed on an overhead shaker for at least 12 h prior to analysis.

Grain size analysis was conducted with a Laser particle counter Mastersizer 3000 (MALVERN). To prevent damage on the instrument from large particles, all material $>1 \text{ mm}$ was sieved before measurement. To account for particles $>1 \text{ mm}$, an additional sieving was done with a 2 mm sieve, and the weights of the 1-2 mm and the $>2 \text{ mm}$ fraction were recorded. Since the laser provides results as volumetric percentages, the weights from the larger fractions were integrated into the data set by assuming a particle density of 2.65 g cm^{-3} . Soil Specific Area (SSA) was given directly from the laser output and was only available for particles $<1 \text{ mm}$. Size distribution, sorting parameters, and median grain sizes were calculated over all grain sizes with the package GRADISTAT (Blott & Pye 2001).

5.3 Data analysis

5.3.1 Significance and correlation

Whenever data sets were compared in this study, it was tested whether observed differences were significant or not. Significant differences indicate that it is unlikely that the observed differences have occurred by random chance alone. Assessing significance is important to increase the probability that conclusions are based on actual patterns in the data, not on random variance (Berry 1986). Appropriate and commonly used statistical tests were applied based on data characteristics. Normality was assessed with the Shapiro-Wilk test, and variance homogeneity with the F-test. If both conditions were met, a Student's *t*-test was applied. When data were not normally distributed, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney *U* test was used. When data were normally distributed but variances differed, Welch's *t*-test (numerical values) or Levene's test (factor groupings included) was applied. All tests and further calculations were conducted in R (R Core Team 2025). For all statistical tests, functions from the *stats* package (version 4.3.3; R Core Team 2025) and *car* package (version 3.1-3; J. Fox & Weisberg 2019) were used. Whether a correlation or difference was significant or not was indicated by the *p*-value. The significance level was chosen at 0.05, and *p*-values below 0.001 are reported as $p < 0.001$.

Linear correlations between selected parameters from the YC24 samples were calculated for the terrestrial and marine data set respectively. The parameters included TOC, TIC, TN, Hg, MeHg, sand content, silt content, clay content, depth, DBD, and SSA. Known autocorrelations between some parameters (e.g., TOC and TN, sand and silt content) were acknowledged. Pearson's correlation coefficient *r* and the associated significance level *p* were computed with the function *rcorr* from the R package *Hmisc* (version 5.2-2; Harrell 2025). The *r*-value is a proxy for the strength of a linear correlation between two parameters, with a range from -1 (strong negative linear correlation) to +1 (strong positive linear correlation). An *r*-value of 0 indicates no linear relationship between two parameters. For visualization, correlation matrices were created using *ggplot* (R package *ggplot2*, version 3.5.0; Wickham 2016).

5.3.2 Modeling mercury concentrations

5.3.2.1 Data preparation

The terrain units from Couture et al. (2018) used in this study cover the entire Yukon coastline and extend approximately 2 km inland. Each terrain unit is further divided vertically into one up to 48 layers, each assumed to have uniform physical and geochemical characteristics and a consistent Hg concentration. To calculate onshore Hg stocks and fluxes, the aim was to determine a Hg concentration for each terrain unit and layer. In addition to the results from own samples collected during the YC24 expedition, 217 samples from the AWI Potsdam archive were analyzed for their Hg content in the same way as described in section 5.2.2, thereby extending the data set for this study. More Hg concentrations were harvested from other studies. All available Hg concentrations were assigned to their respective terrain unit and layer, depending on sample location and depth. Where multiple data points existed for a single layer, the arithmetic mean from all measurements was used. Samples YC24_T2, YC24_T3, and YC24_T4—taken from mud pools, stabilized zones, and thaw streams within Slump D—were excluded, as they derive from disturbed sites and are not considered representative for their terrain unit.

5.3.2.2 Random forest model

From all data collected, Hg concentrations could be assigned to 158 out of 508 layers from 21 out of 44 terrain units (Fig. 6, step 1). For layers lacking measured values, Hg concentrations were estimated using a random forest model. This type of model is an ensemble learning method that combines the outcomes of many decision trees and thereby improves prediction accuracy and controls overfitting (Breiman 2001). Each tree is trained on a random subset of data and the final prediction is made by averaging the results (Breiman 2001). In this case, predictor variables comprised latitude, longitude, mean depth, minimum depth, maximum depth, TOC content, DBD, grain size class, slope score, and land cover (Tab. 3). Those predictor variables were chosen based on the Boruta algorithm using the *Boruta* function (R package *Boruta*, version 8.0.0; Kursa & Rudnicki 2010) in R (Fig. 6, step 2). This algorithm evaluates the importance of potential predictor variables by comparing shuffled values of a variable with the original order of the values (Kursa & Rudnicki 2010). In

this case, only one potential predictor (whether a layer belonged to the active layer or permafrost) was excluded by the algorithm. Predictor values were obtained from different sources according to Table 3. The order of importance of the predictors was assessed using the *FeatureImp* function from the package *iml* (version 0.11.4; Molnar et al. 2018), which measures the importance “as the factor by which the model’s prediction error increases when the feature is shuffled” (Molnar et al. 2018). Error bars represent the variation in the estimated variable importance due to random permutations.

Table 3: Random forest model predictors, their source, and how the data were prepared for the model. A more detailed description of the data preparation can be found in the text below.

Data	Reference	Data preparation
Latitude, longitude, mean depth, minimum depth, maximum depth, TOC content, DBD	Couture et al. 2018	Adding coordinates where missing; including own TOC measurements
Grain size class, slope score	CanCoast 2.0 data set (Manson et al. 2019)	Assignment according to sample location (grain size) and longest coastline section (slope score)
Land cover (LANDC), 21 classes	Bartsch et al. 2019	Determining main land cover classes and their coverage (in %)

Since not all data were following the same separation as the one given by the terrain units, data preparation was necessary. Where no coordinates were given by Couture et al. (2018), a center point of the respective terrain unit was chosen for latitude and longitude values. TOC values from Couture et al. (2018) were replaced where own TOC measurements were available. The grain size class, where the sample points of a terrain unit fell in, was assigned to the respective terrain unit. The assigned slope score of a terrain unit represents the longest part of the respective terrain unit. The determination was done by intersecting the CanCoast slope layer (polyline) with the terrain unit layer (polygon) in QGIS (version 3.42.0). The length of each segment of the lines was calculated, and by using the Group

Stats plugin (version 2.2.7) the longest section and its respective slope score were determined. The only exception was Roland Bay NW, where the slope score of the exposed coastline was assigned instead of that of the longest section. This deviation was made because Roland Bay has an extended stretch of coastline along the inland-lying bay that is probably not the main area of active erosion. The LANDC file (Bartsch et al. 2019) was clipped to the terrestrial part of the study area in QGIS. Using the function *extract* (R package *terra*, version 1.7-71; Hijmans 2025), their respective terrain unit was assigned to all raster cells. From this, the land cover classes that occurred in each terrain unit were determined and the top five land cover classes (LC classX) and their coverage (LC percentX in %) were kept as predictors for the random forest model. Since no (potential) training data and predictor values were available, no model was trained for marine sediment Hg concentrations.

Model training followed the procedure suggested by Vaysse & Lagacherie (2017) and is depicted in Figure 6 (step 3). The model was trained 200 times, each time using a different separation of training and validation data. The training data set always contained 75 % of the data points per terrain unit to ensure good spatial coverage for model training. The model was fitted in R using the *quantregForest* function of the *quantregForest* package (version 1.3-7.1; Meinshausen 2024). This random forest algorithm does not only save the mean of the observations at each terminal node of the different trees (as it is done by the “basic” random forest algorithm), but the values of all observations at this node, which allows for an assessment of the distribution and uncertainty of the prediction (Vaysse & Lagacherie 2017). The number of trees (*ntree*) was set to 500. The number of variables that were to be considered at each node (*mtry*) was determined by testing at which value the correlation between predictions and actual measurements was highest, which was found at *mtry* = 13 (out of a total of 19 variables). The median and the 95 % quantiles of each prediction were stored. To assess model quality, accuracy plots were created (plotting actual vs predicted values) and the linear correlation coefficient between actual and mean predicted concentration was calculated. Whether the correlation was significant or not was tested with the function *cor.test* in R (package *stats*, version 4.3.3; R Core Team 2025). Other parameters considered for model evaluation were the Root Mean Squared Error RMSE (Eq. (2))

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (c_i - \hat{c}_i)^2}{N}} \quad (2)$$

and the coefficient of determination (R^2 ; percentage of explained variance) (Eq. (3))

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (c_i - \hat{c}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N (c_i - \bar{c})^2}, \quad (3)$$

with N = number of data points, c_i = actual concentration of data point i , \hat{c}_i = predicted concentration of data point i , and \bar{c} = mean of actual concentrations.

Figure 6: Workflow of Hg modelling using a random forest model. Hg was predicted for 586 data points (instead of just 508) to consider all available information.

5.3.2.3 Prediction and uncertainty

Following the robustness assessment, the model was built one more time, this time using all available Hg values (not only 75 %) from the training data and their corresponding predictor values ($n = 158$; Fig. 6, step 4). The prediction of the Hg concentrations for the unknown data points ($n = 468$) was conducted using this final model. Again, the 95 % quantiles were saved along with the median predictions. Where Hg concentrations were given from own measurements, the uncertainty was assigned from the standard deviation of the standard measured along with the samples in the mercury analyzer. This allowed to assess the range of possible Hg concentrations for all terrain units and layers. Where several data points were available for one layer, the average of the Hg concentrations and uncertainties was used for further calculation (Fig. 6, step 5).

5.3.2.4 Simpler approaches

Many studies reported a strong positive correlation between OM content and Hg concentrations (Fox et al. 2014; Bełdowska et al. 2016; Rutkowski et al. 2021; Du et al. 2024). When this relationship is weak or not statistically significant, stronger correlations are often found when splitting the data set into one or several subsets, based on TOC content (Schuster et al. 2018; Lim et al. 2020; Tarbier et al. 2021). In this study, the following thresholds were chosen based on expert knowledge: TOC content below 5 %, between 5 and 17 %, and above 17 % (Gustaf Hugelius & Rachele Lodi, personal communication). In both cases, this approach allows for predicting Hg concentrations from known TOC values. Both approaches (one ratio or three classes) were also tested in this study.

5.3.3 Estimating stocks & fluxes

Based on the actual and predicted Hg concentrations in the different terrain units and layers, Hg stocks and fluxes for the Yukon coast were calculated. First, the Hg stock per layer and square meter was calculated according to Equation (4):

$$M_{Hg} = DBD \times h \times \frac{c_{Hg}}{100\%}, \quad (4)$$

where M_{Hg} = Hg mass [kg m^{-2}], DBD = dry bulk density [kg m^{-3}], h = layer thickness [m], and c_{Hg} = Hg concentration [%]. Including DBD here ensures that the volume of pore ice and fine ice lenses is accounted for. Next, the Hg mass was corrected for massive ground ice and wedge ice volume using layer-specific ice fractions V_{ice} [%] from Couture et al. (2018) (Eq. (5)). The corrected stock $M_{Hg,corr}$ became:

$$M_{Hg,corr} = M_{Hg} - \left(M_{Hg} \times \frac{V_{ice}}{100\%} \right). \quad (5)$$

Summing $M_{Hg,corr}$ over all layers yields the total Hg mass per square meter for each terrain unit ($M_{Hg,tu}$). The mass of Hg stored in the entire Yukon coast was calculated by multiplying $M_{Hg,tu}$ with the terrestrial area of each terrain unit and summing those stocks up. To obtain annual fluxes, $M_{Hg,tu}$ was multiplied by the yearly eroded area of each terrain unit [$\text{m}^2 \text{yr}^{-1}$] (data from Couture et al. 2018) and then (a) divided by the unit's coastline length [m], giving a flux in [$\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$] for better comparison between the terrain units, and (b) summed up to obtain the total flux of Hg from the Yukon coast.

Uncertainties of Hg stocks and fluxes were calculated in the same way as the best estimate. For uncertainty calculation, the mean upper and lower boundary of the 95 % quantiles were used as upper and lower boundaries of stocks and fluxes for all predicted Hg concentrations. Where Hg concentrations were given, the upper and lower boundaries of the 95 % quantiles were calculated from the respective standard deviation ($c_{Hg} \pm 2 \times \text{standard deviation}$).

6 Results

6.1 Geochemical parameters

6.1.1 Total mercury

Hg concentrations in terrestrial samples ranged from $18.33 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (sample YC24_T7_4, terrain unit Clarence Lagoon, 50-65 cm depth) to $271.8 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (sample PG2163_003-008, terrain unit Herschel Island N, 0-10 cm depth), with an overall mean of $74.52 \pm 29.91 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 158$). Concentrations were generally higher in the active layer (maximum depth: 1.5 m), which exhibited a mean value of $84.59 \pm 47.26 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 37$), compared to the permafrost below, where the mean was $71.44 \pm 21.45 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 121$). From the measured data, this difference was not significant ($p = 0.312$) but became significant in the modelled data ($p < 0.001$). Spatially, samples from HIQ showed significantly ($p = 0.004$) higher Hg concentrations, with a mean of $85.47 \pm 35.08 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 39$), than those from the Yukon mainland coast (mean = $70.76 \pm 27.29 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 118$). Along the mainland coast, a pronounced east-west gradient was observed, with samples located east of -138.4°W (Babbage River Delta) exhibiting more than double as high concentrations (mean = $96.49 \pm 24.98 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 28$) than those west of -139.5°W (Malcom River fan; mean = $39.34 \pm 9.9 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 22$) (Fig. 7). These spatial trends—higher concentrations at HIQ and in the eastern sampling area—were significant and also found in the modeled Hg concentrations.

Figure 7: Terrestrial sediment Hg concentrations across the longitudinal gradient of the YCP from west (W) to east (E).

In marine sediment samples, Hg concentrations were significantly lower on average than those in terrestrial samples ($p < 0.001$), ranging from $4.37 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (sample P4, Simpson Point, 0-2 cm depth) to $159.96 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (sample 42-06, Kay Point, 0-2 cm depth), with an average value of $52.04 \pm 27.93 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 87$). Mean Hg concentrations were significantly higher ($p < 0.001$) in deeper samples (below 2 cm depth; $67.39 \pm 14.4 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 28$) compared to surface samples (0-2 cm depth; $44.75 \pm 29.88 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 59$). Surface samples exhibited greater variability, with a wider range (4.37 to $159.96 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) than non-surface samples (13.97 to $94.84 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). Hg concentrations were significantly ($p = 0.022$) elevated in marine sediment samples collected around HIQ, with an average concentration of $55.26 \pm 21.66 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 61$), compared to those along the mainland coast (mean = $44.48 \pm 38.38 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 26$) (Fig. 8). A discernible east-west gradient was observed also in marine sediment samples, with eastern samples (east of -138.4°W) exhibiting about ten times higher mean concentrations ($90.31 \pm 35.2 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 7$) compared to western samples (west of -139.5°W), which had a mean of $9.72 \pm 2.3 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 3$). This difference was significant ($p = 0.017$). No consistent spatial pattern in Hg distribution was observed with increasing distance from the shore.

Figure 8: Marine sediment Hg concentrations across the longitudinal gradient of the YCP from west (W) to east (E).

6.1.2 Methylmercury

MeHg concentrations were determined for all YC24 samples. Across the terrestrial samples, MeHg concentrations ranged from $0.064 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (YC24_T7_6, cliff at the Yukon coast, 110 cm depth) to $1.24 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (YC24_T2_2, mud pool from Slump D, 20 cm depth), with a mean of $0.29 \pm 0.25 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 52$). Concentrations generally decreased with depth, with the highest concentrations found in the upper 30 cm (mean = $0.38 \pm 0.28 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 26$), followed by an average concentration of $0.22 \pm 0.21 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ between 30 and 100 cm ($n = 17$), and lowest mean concentrations below 100 cm depth ($0.14 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 9$). Differences between the upper 30 cm and the other depth ranges were significant ($p < 0.001$). When comparing the three different sampling regions, average MeHg concentrations were similar between Slump D on HIQ ($0.28 \pm 0.23 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 38$) and the Yukon mainland coast ($0.30 \pm 0.297 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 14$), and lower in marine sediments ($0.21 \pm 0.08 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 24$), but those differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Within Slump D, the highest MeHg concentrations were found in mud pools (mean = $0.41 \pm 0.32 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 9$), followed by sediments in thaw streams ($0.27 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 3$) and stabilized zones ($0.27 \pm 0.08 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 6$) (Fig. 9). Differences were not significant. Samples from the undisturbed tundra on top of Slump D and from the headwall of Slump D exhibited significantly lower concentrations (mean = $0.23 \pm 0.21 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 22$) than those found within the RTS, with three times higher mean concentrations in the active layer ($0.49 \pm 0.43 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 4$) than in permafrost samples ($0.17 \pm 0.06 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 18$) ($p = 0.002$). For the mainland coast samples, similar depth-related significant trends were observed, with undisturbed active layer samples showing more than three times higher mean MeHg concentrations ($0.61 \pm 0.36 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 4$) compared to permafrost ($0.18 \pm 0.19 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 8$).

Figure 9: Terrestrial sediment MeHg concentrations from different parent material types and locations. Stabilized zones and thaw stream samples originated from Slump D only, while active layer, permafrost, and mud pools samples came from Slump D and the mainland coast.

In marine sediments ($n = 24$), MeHg concentrations were generally lower than in terrestrial samples with a range from $0.08 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (YC24_T5_2, beach at Slump D, 15 cm depth) to $0.38 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (YC24_MC1_4_2-7cm, 800 m distance to shore, 2-7 cm depth) and a mean of $0.21 \pm 0.08 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Higher MeHg concentrations were found with increasing distance to shore (Fig. 10), with a mean concentration of $0.12 \pm 0.07 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 5$) within the first 200 m and an about twofold significantly higher mean concentration of $0.27 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 11$) beyond 600 m offshore ($p = 0.002$). Concentrations also tended to increase with sediment depth. Subsurface samples (> 2 cm depth) showed a (not significantly, $p = 0.15$) higher mean concentration ($0.23 \pm 0.09 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 11$) than surface samples ($0.19 \pm 0.07 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 13$).

Figure 10: Marine sediment MeHg concentrations from grab samples and short sediment cores along a 2000 m offshore transect from the southeast coast of HIQ in front of Slump D. The water depth is compressed for improved data visualization.

The proportion of MeHg relative to total Hg (%MeHg) ranged from 0.07 % (YC24_TC2_7, permafrost from undisturbed tundra at Slump D, 72 cm depth) to 2.85 % (YC24_T7_1, active layer from Yukon coast, 20 cm depth) for terrestrial samples, with a mean of 0.53 ± 0.59 % ($n = 52$). Marine sediment samples showed a smaller range from 0.15 % (YC24_T5_2, marine beach, 0 m offshore) to 0.89 % (YC24_MC1_1_2-4cm, 4 m water depth, 200 m offshore) with a mean of 0.38 ± 0.14 %, which did not differ significantly from the terrestrial mean. Differences in %MeHg between active layer and permafrost samples were significant ($p = 0.006$), with an almost four times higher mean %MeHg in active layers (1.21 ± 1.03 %, $n = 8$) than in permafrost samples (0.31 ± 0.32 %, $n = 26$).

6.1.3 Carbon and nitrogen

TOC concentrations in terrestrial samples ranged from 0.5 % (Komakuk Beach, 4 m depth) to 49.42 % (Phillips Bay, 55 cm depth), with a mean of 9.23 % across the full data set (all terrain units and layers, $n = 586$). For the YC24 subset, the TOC range was similar, although the mean was lower at 6.58 % ($n = 52$). Total Inorganic Carbon (TIC) concentrations were considerably lower and ranged from 0.11 to 1.89 % ($n = 35$), with 17 samples having TIC concentrations below the detection limit of 0.1 %. Excluding those, the mean TIC concentration was 0.78 ± 0.46 %. TOC contents were double as high in the active layer (mean = 14.15 ± 13.84 %, $n = 136$) than in permafrost (mean = 7.75 ± 10.08 %, $n = 450$). This significant trend was also observed, but not significant, within the YC24 subset, where undisturbed active layer samples showed higher TOC values (mean = 11.51 ± 13.09 %, $n = 8$) than permafrost samples (mean = 8.16 ± 8.01 %, $n = 26$). In contrast, when including disturbed unfrozen samples from Slump D (i.e., mud pools, stabilized zones, thaw streams), this trend reversed and TOC concentrations in permafrost (8.16 %) exceeded those in the active layer (mean = 5 ± 8.24 %, $n = 26$), though not significantly ($p = 0.071$).

TN concentrations (in YC24 samples) varied from 0.11 % (YC24_T1_4, 200 cm depth) to 2.72 % (YC24_T8_1, 20 cm depth), with a mean of 0.46 % ($n = 52$). TN values showed a similar pattern as TOC concentrations: in undisturbed YC24 active layer samples, TN concentrations were higher (mean = 0.82 ± 0.86 %, $n = 8$) than in permafrost samples (mean = 0.51 ± 0.44 %, $n = 26$), but including disturbed active layer samples resulted in a lower TN mean in non-permafrost samples (0.4 ± 0.54 %, $n = 26$)

compared to permafrost samples. In both cases, the differences were not significant ($p > 0.05$).

TOC and TN concentrations were generally enriched in surface layers (Fig. 11). Samples from the upper meter had a mean TOC concentration of $12.87 \pm 12.7\%$ ($n = 268$) and a mean TN concentration of $0.48 \pm 0.54\%$ ($n = 43$), while samples below one meter averaged $6.17 \pm 9.08\%$ TOC ($n = 318$; significantly lower) and $0.34 \pm 0.21\%$ TN ($n = 9$; no significant difference). Spatial differences in TOC and TN distribution were evident. The mainland coast exhibited a more than twofold higher mean TOC concentration ($10.96 \pm 12.34\%$, $n = 422$) than HIQ (mean = $4.81 \pm 6.63\%$, $n = 164$), a trend consistent across both the full data set and the YC24 samples (but significant only for the full data set). Along the mainland coast, TOC concentrations varied regionally: the eastern part ($> -138.4^\circ\text{W}$) had a significantly lower mean TOC concentration ($8.35 \pm 9.27\%$, $n = 166$) compared to the western part ($< -139.5^\circ\text{W}$; mean = $13.35 \pm 13.94\%$, $n = 111$) (Fig. 12). TN concentrations were also higher (but not significantly higher) at the mainland coast (mean = $0.68 \pm 0.78\%$, $n = 14$) than at Slump D (mean = $0.37 \pm 0.31\%$, $n = 38$). The TN distribution along the YCP could not be assessed due to all YC24 samples originating from the western unit.

Figure 11: Vertical distribution of Hg, MeHg, TOC, and TN in terrestrial sediments from active layer, permafrost, mud pools, stabilized zones, and thaw streams.

Figure 12: TOC distribution across terrain units and layers of the YCP from west (W) to east (E).

The atomic TOC/TN (C/N) ratio in terrestrial sediments ranged from 1.5 (YC24_TC1_2, tundra on top of Slump D, 33 cm depth) to 20.9 (YC24_T1_1, Slump D headwall, 20 cm depth) with one outstanding C/N ratio for sample YC24_TC1_2 (top of permafrost, Slump D headwall, 33 cm depth) with a ratio of 60.1. On average, Slump D exhibited higher (but not significantly higher) C/N ratios (16.6 ± 7.7 , $n = 38$) than the Yukon coast (12 ± 5.7 , $n = 14$). Within Slump D, the C/N ratios across different landscape types (mud pools, stabilized zones, thaw streams) were relatively consistent, with average values between 11.6 and 15.3. This was significantly lower than the C/N ratios of the undisturbed tundra around Slump D (18.5 ± 9.6 , $n = 22$). Overall, terrestrial C/N ratios were significantly lower in surficial samples (0-30 cm; mean = 13.8 ± 3.3 , $n = 26$) than in deeper layers (> 30 cm; mean = 17.3 ± 9.6 , $n = 26$), and in non-permafrost samples (13.8 ± 3.4 , $n = 26$) than in permafrost samples (17.3 ± 9.6 , $n = 26$).

Marine sediment samples (here: YC24 samples and data from literature and other publications) exhibited generally low TOC concentrations with a mean of 1.72 ± 1.84 % ($n = 87$), ranging from 0.24 % (Whale Bay, 0-2 cm sediment depth) to 15.32 % (Nunaluk Spit, 30 m offshore, 0-2 cm sediment depth). Deeper sediments showed significantly higher TOC levels (mean = 1.94 ± 1.05 %, $n = 28$) compared to surface sediments (mean = 1.61 ± 2.12 %, $n = 59$) ($p = 0.001$), but surface sediments demonstrated a considerably broader range (0.24 % to 15.32 %) than deeper samples (0.54 % to 6.8 %). Along the mainland coast, marine TOC concentrations were more than ten times higher in the eastern region east of -138.4°W (90.31 ± 35.2 %, $n = 7$) compared to the western part west of -139.5°W (5.66 ± 8.36 %, $n = 3$). The difference was significant ($p = 0.017$), but the database was very small. No trend in TOC concentration in relation to the distance from shore was found.

TN concentrations, available for the marine YC24 samples and data from Petzold (2024) ($n = 31$), were comparable between surface sediments (mean = 0.09 %, $n = 15$) and deeper layers (mean = 0.12 %, $n = 13$). Although distance to shore rarely influenced TN levels, it is noteworthy that the eleven samples with TN values below detection limit (i.e., < 0.1 %) were collected within the first 600 m offshore (Fig. 13). Those eleven samples also exhibited the highest C/N ratios averaging 93.7 (assuming TN = 0.05 %). The four highest and lowest C/N ratios (24.34 to 32.16 and 11.1 to 12.6, respectively) originated from these samples, assuming TN = 0.05 %. Excluding those values, the ratio in marine samples ranged from 13.2 to 19.7. The

mean C/N ratio of marine samples (17 ± 2 , $n = 20$; excluding highest and lowest values) was significantly higher ($p = 0.008$) than the one in terrestrial samples (15.6 ± 7.3 , $n = 52$). Within marine samples, the ratio was slightly but not significantly ($p = 0.072$) higher in surface sediments (17.8 ± 1.7 , $n = 11$) than below 2 cm sediment depth (16.3 ± 2 , $n = 12$). No trend was observed with distance to shore (Fig. 13).

Figure 13: Distribution of Hg, TOC, TN, C/N ratio, MeHg, and SSA in marine sediments along the transect in front of Slump D ($n = 24$). Connected dots represent surface sediments (0-2 cm depth), while transparent dots show values of samples of greater depth (up to 37 cm).

6.1.4 Grain size distribution

Grain size distribution was available for all terrestrial and marine YC24 samples. Terrestrial sediment samples predominantly consisted of medium to coarse silt (Fig. 14), with median grain sizes ranging from $5.97 \mu\text{m}$ (YC24_T1_6, Slump D headwall, 100 cm depth) to $59.07 \mu\text{m}$ (YC24_T7_1, mainland coast bluff, 20 cm depth).

Across landscape types, grain size distributions tended to be consistent within their sampling location, even when samples were taken at different depths (Appendix, Fig. 31). Notable exceptions included site YC24_T7 (Yukon coast bluff), where samples from 20 cm (YC24_T7_1) and 65 cm depth (YC24_T7_4) exhibited a pronounced increase in volume of grains around 63 μm , in contrast to other YC24_T7 samples. At site YC24_T1 (Slump D headwall) grain size profiles varied slightly with depth: higher sand and gravel fractions were observed in the active layer (mean sand + gravel proportion = 20.6 %, $n = 2$), at 50 cm depth (34.2 %), and at 200 cm depth (45.4 %), while the intermediate section (between 50 and 200 cm) showed a finer composition (mean sand + gravel proportion = 10.9 %, $n = 2$).

Specific surface area (SSA) was used as a proxy for grain size distribution. SSA values were similar between permafrost and non-permafrost samples, indicating no distinct textural shift across the thermal boundary. Spatial differences, however, were evident. Samples from Slump D contained significantly finer material than those from the Yukon coast. This was reflected in significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher SSA values at Slump D (mean = $1543.7 \pm 228.1 \text{ m}^2 \text{ kg}^{-1}$, $n = 38$) compared to the Yukon coast (mean = $914.2 \pm 231 \text{ m}^2 \text{ kg}^{-1}$, $n = 14$). Within the slump, mud pools and stabilized zones showed similar grain size characteristics and SSA values, whereas thaw streams contained slightly and significantly finer sediments, with SSA values averaging at $1819 \pm 109 \text{ m}^2 \text{ kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 3$), compared to approximately $1588 \pm 154 \text{ m}^2 \text{ kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 13$) on the slump floor (mud pools and stabilized zones).

Grain size distribution in marine sediment samples exhibited a wide range (Fig. 14), with median grain size spanning from 5.23 μm (YC24_MC1_2, 8 cm sediment depth, 6 m water depth, 400 m offshore) to 561.53 μm (YC24_T5_2, marine beach, 15 cm sediment depth). Coarse fractions (sand and gravel) were predominantly found near the beach and in the nearshore area, while finer sediments became increasingly dominant with greater distance from the coast and increasing water depth. Samples collected beyond 600 m offshore had a significantly ($p = 0.038$) lower mean median grain size of $8.98 \pm 2.21 \mu\text{m}$ ($n = 11$), in contrast to those within the first 200 m, which averaged $240.15 \pm 216.14 \mu\text{m}$ ($n = 5$). Trends with sediment depth were apparent but not significant ($p = 0.084$): surface sediments showed higher median grain sizes (mean = $107.18 \pm 163.18 \mu\text{m}$, $n = 14$) compared to subsurface layers below 2 cm depth (mean = $23.16 \pm 39.82 \mu\text{m}$, $n = 10$).

Figure 14: Grain size distribution of YC24 samples of different types from Slump D, the mainland coast, and marine sediment samples.

6.2 Correlation matrices

Correlation patterns were investigated for the YC24 samples ($n = 76$), where most data were available for. It is acknowledged that there are autocorrelations between several parameters, such as those for grain sizes (sand, silt, clay, SSA) or between TOC and TN (both forming organic material).

6.2.1 Terrestrial samples

In terrestrial samples (YC24 samples, $n = 52$), very few strong and significant ($p < 0.05$) linear correlations were found (Fig. 15). Strongest correlations occurred between autocorrelated parameters, namely SSA & clay ($r = 0.99$), TOC & TN ($r = 0.98$), and sand & silt ($r = -0.85$). Other than that, DBD correlated significantly with TN ($r = -0.75$) and consequently with TOC ($r = -0.74$), as well as with Hg concentrations ($r = -0.51$). Apart from this, Hg only showed significant correlations with the autocorrelated parameters clay ($r = 0.54$) and SSA ($r = 0.55$), and with TIC ($r = -0.75$). MeHg concentrations did not correlate significantly and strongly with any of the analyzed parameters.

Figure 15: Correlation matrix of field and geochemical parameters in terrestrial sediment samples ($n = 52$). The number in each box gives the respective linear correlation coefficient r . Grey values indicate that the correlation was not significant ($p > 0.05$).

6.2.2 Marine samples

In strong contrast to results from terrestrial samples, many parameters in marine sediments ($n = 24$) were strongly and statistically significantly correlated, with most correlations being positive (Fig. 16). Sand content and TIC were notable exceptions, showing mostly negative correlations. Hg in marine samples showed particularly strong positive correlations with clay ($r = 0.95$), SSA ($r = 0.95$), and TN ($r = 0.89$). Hg and MeHg were positively correlated with one another ($r = 0.69$), and MeHg generally correlated significantly with most parameters, which had not been the case in terrestrial samples. Depth did not show any significant correlations with other parameters, and correlations with DBD were generally weaker and mostly negative.

Figure 16: Correlation matrix of field and geochemical parameters in marine sediment samples ($n = 24$). The number in each box gives the respective linear correlation coefficient r . Grey values indicate that the correlation was not significant ($p > 0.05$).

Other significant correlations with Hg included a strong positive correlation between Hg and TOC in stabilized zones ($r = 0.94$, $p = 0.005$, $n = 6$). In mud pools ($n = 9$), Hg correlated negatively with DBD ($r = -0.92$, $p < 0.001$) and TIC ($r = -0.82$, $p = 0.007$), and showed positive correlations with TOC ($r = 0.76$, $p = 0.018$), clay ($r = 0.83$, $p = 0.006$) and SSA ($r = 0.85$, $p = 0.004$). The positive correlation of Hg with clay and SSA was also found in undisturbed active layer samples ($r = 0.81$, $p = 0.015$, and $r = 0.84$, $p = 0.01$, respectively, $n = 8$).

6.3 Mercury stocks & fluxes from the Yukon coast

6.3.1 Model evaluation

Based on training and validation data, the mean correlation across 200 model runs was 0.7 (range from 0.61 to 0.77; $p < 0.001$). The accuracy plot is shown in Figure 17. While the 95 % quantiles for each prediction given by the *quantregForest* algorithm were wide, the median concentrations across runs did not differ significantly from each other. This indicates high uncertainties within the individual predictions, rather than between model runs.

Figure 17: Accuracy plot showing the relationship between actual and predicted Hg concentrations from the 158 training data points. The blue line depicts the optimal ratio of 1 between actual and predicted values.

The R^2 value from the validation data indicated that 42.2 % of the variance in measured Hg concentrations could be explained by the predictor variables, while the rest (57.8 %) must be attributed to unknown variables. Validation data gave an RMSE of $22.67 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 158$). This was below the standard deviation of the analyzed samples, which was at $29.91 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. The importance of the predictors is shown in Figure 18. Mean and maximum depth together with TOC content of the respective layers were the most important predictors. Other important predictors included longitude, the fourth most occurring land cover class (LC class4), minimum depth, and grain size description. Land coverage and slope were the least important.

Figure 18: Importance assessment of the predictors used for the random forest model. The higher the value, the higher the increase in RMSE if the respective predictor would be omitted from the model, and the more important this variable was. LC classX represents the one to five most occurring land cover classes, LC percentX is the coverage in % of the respective land cover class per terrain unit.

For comparison, two more approaches other than the random forest model were tested for predicting Hg concentrations based on the Hg:TOC ratio, which is often used to predict Hg concentrations from known TOC content. The statistical results are shown in Table 4. The correlations were mostly weak and only significant ($p < 0.05$) for the group with TOC < 5%. Due to these weak correlations, these approaches were not used for further calculations, but the total stocks and fluxes that resulted from the ratios given above are reported in chapters 6.3.3 and 6.3.4.

Table 4: Statistical results from Hg:TOC ratios. The total number of samples (n), the resulting ratio from the respective data set, the linear correlation coefficient between Hg and TOC (r) and the significance level (p) are given.

Data set	n	Hg:TOC ratio	r-value	p-value
1) All data	158	1.3	0.14	0.084
2) Splitting the data				
TOC < 5 %	72	3.69	0.23	0.047
5 % ≤ TOC ≤ 17 %	50	0.9	0.28	0.053
TOC > 17 %	36	0.23	0.19	0.256

6.3.2 Predictions

Following random forest model tuning and evaluation, the model was applied to predict Hg concentrations for all unknown layers. Resulting median predictions and 95 % quantiles are depicted in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Predicted Hg concentrations for surface and deeper samples from the random forest model across the longitudinal gradient of the YCP from west (W) to east (E). Here, surface samples represent the uppermost layer only, while *deeper* refers to all other layers.

A wide range in predicted Hg concentrations became obvious. The highest concentrations and ranges were predicted for surface layers (upper 5 to 10 cm) with a TOC content of 25 % and a DBD of 310 kg m^{-3} ($n = 28$). Excluding those high concentrations, the predictions ranged from 30.46 to $110.28 \text{ µg kg}^{-1}$, with a mean of $66.84 \pm 18.58 \text{ µg kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 414$). When examining the vertical distribution of Hg, mean concentration in the top 1 m of soil was $84.65 \pm 53.89 \text{ µg kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 234$), compared to $65.71 \pm 19.02 \text{ µg kg}^{-1}$ below ($n = 274$). Despite this significant difference ($p < 0.001$), the top 1 m accounted for only 6.1 % of the total Hg content of the YCP. The lateral and vertical distribution of predicted Hg concentrations is shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Average Hg concentrations per terrain unit and layer from measured and predicted data from west (W) to east (E).

Hg concentrations in the top 1 m varied across the six surficial materials of the YCP (Fig. 21) which were given from Couture et al. (2018). Significant differences were identified with statistical tests. As the assumptions for Analysis of Variances (ANOVA; normal distribution of residuals, homogeneity of variances) were not met, a Kruskal-Wallis test was applied as a non-parametric alternative, followed by Dunn's Kruskal-Wallis test for pairwise comparisons (package *FSA*, version 0.9.6, Ogle et al. 2025). To control for multiple comparisons, Holm-adjusted p -values (p_{adj}) were considered. From this, the differences between the three pairs Ice-thrust moraine & Glacial outwash, Ice-thrust moraine & Marine beach, and Rolling moraine & Glacial outwash were statistically significant ($p_{adj} < 0.05$). No clear concentration pattern appeared across material types.

Figure 21: Hg concentrations in the upper 1 m across the six lithologies of the YCP.

6.3.3 Stocks

The estimated total Hg stock of the Yukon coast based on the measurements and the outcomes of the random forest model amounts to approximately 381,080 kg (95 % prediction interval = 271,540 to 501,930 kg). The highest stocks were found at the terrain unit King Point NW, reaching 2.6 g Hg m⁻², while the lowest stocks occurred at Whale Bay W with 0.04 g Hg m⁻². The overall mean Hg stock was 0.61 g Hg m⁻². Spatially, stocks were greater in the eastern part of the study area compared to the western region (Fig. 22). A strong positive relationship between bluff height

and Hg stock was observed, reflecting the increase in soil volume with increasing bluff elevation ($r = 0.93$, $p < 0.001$).

Figure 22: Hg stocks [g m^{-2}] of the Yukon coast.

Hg stocks were compared between study sections using uniform volumes of one cubic meter to account for different bluff heights of the different terrain units (Fig. 23). Stocks ranged from 0.02 g m^{-3} (Workboat Passage E) to 0.15 g m^{-3} (Simpson Point). From these calculations, stocks were highest at section 2, and lowest in sections 1 and 4, which were less affected by the Last Glacial Maximum than other sections. The variability of Hg stocks across sections was considerable. Whether differences were significant was tested by performing multiple pairwise-comparisons between the means of the groups, using the Tukey 'Honest Significant Difference' method (function *TukeyHSD*, package *stats*, version 4.3.3, R Core Team 2025) as normality and homogeneity of variances were given (confirmed with Shapiro-Wilk and Levene tests). Only section 2 differed significantly from sections 1, 3, 4, 5, and 8. Large variability was obvious within sections, indicating substantial heterogeneity that was not covered by the division of sections.

Figure 23: Hg stocks [g m^{-3}] across the eight sections of the Yukon coast. For more details about the sections, see Table 1.

To place these results in a broader context, total Hg stocks were also estimated using alternative methods. Applying a single Hg:TOC ratio, as done for instance by Schuster et al. (2018) resulted in a total stock estimate of 147,390 kg Hg—approximately 2.5 times lower than the stock estimated from the random forest model. Splitting the training data into three subsets based on TOC content gave a higher estimate of 232,150 kg (1.5 times lower than the random forest estimate).

6.3.4 Fluxes

The mean coastal erosion rate along the YCP was 0.71 m yr^{-1} , varying considerably across the coast (Tab. 5). Maximum erosion rates exceeding 1 m yr^{-1} were observed west of HIQ, at the terrain unit Herschel Island North (1.2 m yr^{-1}), and in parts of the eastern coast, including Stokes Point (3.58 m yr^{-1}), Kay Point (2.3 m yr^{-1}), and King Point SE (1.1 m yr^{-1}). Some coastal segments were stable (Malcolm River fan with barrier island and Kay Point Spit) or showed accretion (Shingle Point E, Stokes Point SE) (Tab. 5).

Hg fluxes per terrain unit resulting from coastal erosion ranged from -4.7 kg yr^{-1} to 43.2 kg yr^{-1} (Fig. 24), with negative values indicating accumulation. The mean Hg flux amounted to 2.59 kg yr^{-1} . Normalized fluxes per meter of coastline ranged

from $-0.39 \text{ g m}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ to $2.57 \text{ g m}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, with a mean of $0.38 \text{ g m}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. In both cases, the highest fluxes were recorded at Herschel Island N and Herschel Island W, while the highest accumulation took place at Shingle Point E. Overall, Hg release was lower south and southwest of HIQ, and higher in the eastern parts of the study area and at HIQ itself (Fig. 24). The total Hg flux for the entire YCP was estimated at 113 kg yr^{-1} (87 to 163 kg yr^{-1}) considering accumulation (negative) and equilibrium (neutral) at two terrain units, respectively.

Figure 24: Hg fluxes [$\text{g m}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$] from the Yukon coast.

To compare Hg fluxes between sections, the mass of Hg per cubic meter of eroding material was calculated by considering the bluff height and annual change rate. Figure 25 illustrates the distribution of these fluxes across sections. Values ranged from -0.14 (Shingle Point E) to $0.22 \text{ g m}^{-3} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (Simpson Point). The highest Hg release per cubic meter was observed for section 2, where the mean value was significantly higher than in sections 1 and 4. No significant differences were found between the other sections, as determined by a one-way ANOVA test, following the procedure described in chapter 6.3.2. Although the sections were defined based on similar

physical characteristics, the observed variability in Hg flux per cubic meter suggests that these groupings do not reflect uniform behavior with respect to Hg release.

Figure 25: Hg fluxes [$\text{g m}^{-3} \text{yr}^{-1}$] across the eight sections of the Yukon coast. For more details about the sections, see Table 1.

To assess the broader implications for total Hg flux estimates, two simplified approaches were tested. Applying a single Hg:TOC ratio, as done for instance by Schuster et al. (2018), resulted in a total flux estimate of $56.5 \text{ kg Hg yr}^{-1}$ —half the estimate from the random forest model. Subdividing the training data into three subsets gave a higher total Hg flux of 83.7 kg yr^{-1} , which remains 1.4 times lower than the random forest model-based estimate.

Table 5: Section allocation, characteristics, stocks, and fluxes per terrain unit. Change rate and bluff height from Couture et al. (2018).

Terrain unit	Section	Change rate [m yr ⁻¹]	Bluff height [m]	Hg stock [g m ⁻²]	Hg stock [g m ⁻³]	Hg flux [g m ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹]	Hg flux [g m ⁻³ yr ⁻¹]
Clarence Lagoon W	1	-1.6	7.1	0.168	0.024	0.260	0.023
Clarence Lagoon	1	-0.8	1.0	0.065	0.065	0.056	0.070
Clarence Lagoon E	1	-0.9	2.2	0.086	0.039	0.080	0.040
Komakuk Beach W2	1	-1.1	6.7	0.213	0.032	0.242	0.033
Komakuk Beach W1	1	-1.6	6.8	0.137	0.020	0.214	0.020
Komakuk Beach	1	-1.3	6.2	0.142	0.023	0.191	0.024
Malcolm River fan	1	-0.8	1.9	0.073	0.038	0.059	0.039
Malcolm River fan with barrier island	1	0	1.0	0.091	0.091	0	NA
Nunaluk Spit	2	-1.2	1.0	0.093	0.093	0.095	0.079
Avadlek Spit	2	-0.7	1.2	0.143	0.119	0.135	0.161
Herschel Island W	3	-0.9	27.7	1.932	0.070	2.079	0.083
Herschel Island N	3	-1.2	36.0	2.033	0.056	2.587	0.060
Simpson Point	2	-0.5	1.0	0.147	0.147	0.108	0.216
Herschel Island E	3	-0.4	21.8	1.201	0.055	0.490	0.056
Herschel Island S	3	-0.3	11.0	0.879	0.080	0.333	0.101
Workboat Passage W	4	-0.5	6.4	0.193	0.030	0.091	0.028
Workboat Passage E	4	-0.4	2.3	0.046	0.020	0.019	0.021
Catton Point	2	-0.3	1.4	0.161	0.115	0.073	0.174
Whale Bay W	4	-1.0	1.7	0.040	0.024	0.039	0.023
Whale Bay	2	-0.5	1.0	0.119	0.119	0.062	0.124

Whale Bay E	4	-0.2	8.2	0.385	0.047	0.071	0.043
Roland Bay NW	4	-0.3	5.9	0.149	0.025	0.049	0.028
Roland Bay W	5	-0.4	8.4	0.378	0.045	0.169	0.050
Roland Bay E	5	-0.7	8.4	0.702	0.084	0.450	0.077
Stokes Point W	5	-0.9	12.5	0.874	0.070	0.784	0.070
Stokes Point	2	-3.6	1.9	0.223	0.117	0.779	0.114
Stokes Point SE	5	0.5	8.3	0.578	0.070	-0.060	-0.014
Phillips Bay NW	5	-0.4	13.8	1.037	0.075	0.407	0.074
Phillips Bay W	2	-0.5	1.0	0.122	0.122	0.083	0.166
Phillips Bay	5	-0.6	4.7	0.268	0.057	0.256	0.091
Babbage River Delta	6	-1.0	3.2	0.177	0.055	0.202	0.063
Kay Point Spit	2	0	1.0	0.091	0.091	0	NA
Kay Point	7	-2.3	8.5	0.501	0.059	1.122	0.057
Kay Point SE	3	-0.2	26.1	2.093	0.080	0.360	0.069
King Point NW	8	-0.2	32.7	2.601	0.080	0.616	0.094
King Point Lagoon	2	-0.3	1.0	0.121	0.121	0.044	0.147
King Point	8	-0.6	7.4	0.216	0.029	0.225	0.051
King Point SE	8	-1.1	10.2	0.695	0.068	0.749	0.067
Sabine Point W	8	-0.7	20.6	0.789	0.038	0.578	0.040
Sabine Point	8	-0.8	20.6	1.064	0.052	0.867	0.053
Sabine Point E	8	-0.4	19.0	0.494	0.026	0.185	0.024
Shingle Point W	8	-0.2	21.1	1.691	0.080	0.299	0.071
Shingle Point E	8	0.2	13.7	1.515	0.111	-0.391	-0.143
Running River	8	-0.7	22.6	1.944	0.086	1.405	0.089

7 Discussion

7.1 Assessment of outcomes and uncertainties

7.1.1 Model behavior and performance

Spatial parameters were the most influential predictors for modeling Hg distribution along the Yukon coast. The model included commonly used predictors such as TOC, depth below surface, land cover, grain size, and slope (Grigal 2002; Olson et al. 2018; Bishop et al. 2020; Rutkowski et al. 2021). In this study's data set, TOC and depth below surface had the best vertical resolution with individual values per layer. Grain size, widely recognized as an important predictor of Hg due to its influence on sorption capacity for heavy metals (Salonen & Korkka-Niemi 2007), was only available as a general surficial classification from the CanCoast data set without vertical resolution, likely limiting its explanatory power. Slope was selected as a relevant parameter by the Boruta algorithm, but its reliability is limited by the dynamic morphology of the Yukon coast under sea-ice influence and ongoing coastal erosion (Irrgang et al. 2022). Substantial geomorphological changes occur due to bluff erosion and lateral sediment transport along the shore, that affect slope characteristics and thereby limit its reliability as a static predictor. Among all available predictors, spatial variables (depth and longitude) showed the highest predictive importance, indicated by RMSE increases when omitting the respective predictor (increases of 5.96, 5.3, 3.13, and 2.93 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for mean depth, maximum depth, minimum depth, and longitude, respectively; Fig. 18). The importance of spatial data is due to both spatial autocorrelation of near things, that "are more related than distant things" (Tobler's First Law of Geography), and the relatively higher precision of these spatial data compared to the other environmental predictors. The strong influence of spatial variables likely compensates for the limited availability and resolution of other key parameters, stressing the need for high-resolution environmental data in future models.

The model predicted a strikingly uniform pattern of Hg concentrations at greater depths, which likely reflects the lack of depth-resolved environmental input data. Low variability was observed in model outcomes for deeper layers (approximately below 1 m depth; Fig. 20). This uniformity could reflect real-world patterns in stable

permafrost zones but seems unusually homogeneous (Olson et al. 2018; Rutkowski et al. 2021) and is likely an artifact of missing vertical detail in predictors. Variables representing the hydrological regime and grain size, which control vertical matter redistribution and sorption processes (Grigal 2002; Chakraborty et al. 2014), were missing or only available for the surface and thus could not capture the subsurface heterogeneity of YCP soils (Rampton 1982; Fritz et al. 2012). This limitation is especially relevant, as hydrological and pedogenic processes vary with depth and can strongly affect Hg mobility and accumulation. Depth-specific environmental data and predictors are essential for a realistic estimation of material concentrations across the entire vertical soil profile, especially where bluffs are high.

Model predictions revealed several unexpected patterns that illustrate the limitations of this model approach when training data are scarce. For example, sandy marine beaches and spits with low cliff heights (~ 1 m) and low TOC content (~ 2 %), belonging to section 2, were predicted to have the highest Hg stocks across all sections (Fig. 23). This finding is counterintuitive, as such landforms and their characteristics do not provide typical conditions for high Hg accumulation (Rutkowski et al. 2021; Du et al. 2024). The relatively elevated Hg stocks of section 2 likely reflect the disproportionate influence of the only available training data point for this section with an above-average measured Hg value of $90.87 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, along with an overall scarcity of low-Hg concentration training samples in the data set (29 out of 158 data points were below $50 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$). The highest measured Hg concentration of $271.8 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ was consistently assigned to surficial layers characterized by a high TOC content of 25 %, a shallow depth ($\leq 10 \text{ cm}$), and a DBD of 310 kg m^{-3} . These predictions were accompanied by wide confidence intervals (Fig. 19), indicating considerable uncertainty. This was probably driven by the large variability within the 11 measured surface samples, where Hg concentrations ranged from 37.97 to $271.8 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Outlier influence and surface variability are two factors driving model uncertainty, which must be addressed by creating a more balanced training data set across the full Hg spectrum and all terrain units to reduce uncertainties.

Key spatial patterns are captured by the random forest algorithm, making it a suitable modeling approach for Hg predictions at the Yukon coast. In this study, the model explained 42.2 % of the observed variance in measured Hg concentrations, outperforming similar models for Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) and nitrogen in the

same region, which reported R^2 values between 10 and 35 % (Wagner et al. 2025). Additionally, the RMSE of $22.67 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ was lower than the standard deviation of measured concentrations ($29.91 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), indicating that the model provided better predictions than a simple mean-based calculation (James et al. 2013). The random forest algorithm has previously been used in similar contexts. Wagner et al. (2025) applied the model to estimate SOC and nitrogen stocks of the YCP, using predictors such as elevation, land cover, vegetation height, and soil wetness. Suleymanov et al. (2023) found random forest to provide the most accurate Hg predictions in urban and peri-urban soils in Ufa, Russia. The modeling approach of this study followed the framework proposed by Vaysse & Lagacherie (2017), which has since been adopted by Xie et al. (2024) and Wagner et al. (2025). These applications collectively support the validity of using random forest for spatial Hg modeling, including data-sparse and dynamic regions such as the permafrost-affected Yukon coast.

The weak correlations between Hg and TOC in this study made the use of Hg:TOC ratios an unreliable method for predicting Hg concentrations from TOC content along the Yukon coast. Across the terrestrial data set with measured Hg concentrations, the correlation between Hg and TOC was not statistically significant ($r = 0.14$, $p = 0.085$), indicating that TOC alone cannot explain the observed variability in Hg content. When applied for upscaling, the total Hg stock was substantially underestimated, amounting to only about one quarter of the estimate derived from the random forest model. While many other studies have found more or less strong linear relationships between Hg and TOC and used this for estimating Hg contents (e.g., Olson et al. 2018; Schuster et al. 2018; Lim et al. 2020), others report similarly weak correlations as found in this study (Xu et al. 2014; Du et al. 2024; Giest et al. 2025), suggesting that the TOC-Hg relationship is not universally robust. Dividing the data into subsets based on TOC content, a method found in previous studies to tweak the correlations (Schuster et al. 2018; Tarbier et al. 2021), did not improve the correlations here either (Tab. 4). The limited explanatory power of TOC may reflect site-specific differences in sediment properties and biogeochemical conditions. Differences in OM composition and origin influence its Hg binding capacity and could explain the differences in correlations between different studies (Douglas et al. 2012; Bishop et al. 2020). For example, Hg tends to bind preferentially to thiol and other sulfur-containing functional groups within OM, which vary in abundance across different organic

sources (Skylberg et al. 2006). Sediment texture is another factor influencing Hg retention as it determines SSA and mineral sorption capacity, thus influencing heavy metal accumulation and considerably controlling Hg distribution (Brigatti et al. 2005; Salonen & Korkka-Niemi 2007). Terrestrial sediments were mainly composed of medium to coarse silt, consistent with previous findings (Fritz et al. 2012), though high heterogeneity and wide ranges in grain size distribution have been observed, particularly on HIQ (Fig. 14; Rampton 1982; Fritz et al. 2012). The positive correlation between Hg and clay content in the YC24 data set ($r = 0.54$, $p = 3.5 \times 10^{-5}$) of this study supports the role of fine particles in Hg retention, while clay content does not fully explain spatial variation in Hg distribution either. The association between Hg and TOC or SSA is clearly context-dependent and should not be generalized without considering site-specific environmental and geochemical factors.

7.1.2 Evaluation and contextualization of mercury stocks and fluxes

Estimated total Hg stocks and fluxes from the Yukon coast fall within the range of existing regional and pan-Arctic assessments, though substantial uncertainties remain due to high uncertainties within model predictions. This study estimated total Hg stocks at the Yukon coast of approximately 381,080 kg (95 % prediction interval = 271,540 to 501,930 kg), with a total flux of 113 kg yr⁻¹ (87 to 163 kg yr⁻¹). Of this annual flux, 65 kg is estimated to originate from HIQ, while only 48 kg comes from the mainland coast. Compared to the only other regional assessment by Leitch (2006), who estimated Hg fluxes of 85 kg yr⁻¹ from HIQ and 165 kg yr⁻¹ from the mainland coast, fluxes from this study are lower, despite higher measured Hg concentrations in the present study. The difference occurs primarily due to the use of updated, terrain unit-specific erosion masses from Couture et al. (2018) in this study (total of 0.84×10^9 kg yr⁻¹), which is about one third compared to the amounts used by Leitch (total of 2.47×10^9 kg yr⁻¹). At the pan-Arctic scale, Outridge et al. (2008) estimated a total Hg input from coastal erosion of 47.3 t yr⁻¹. The Yukon coast's contribution of 113 kg corresponds to 0.24 % of this total estimate. In terms of sediment, the total sediment flux from coastal erosion into the Arctic Ocean has been estimated at 430 Tg yr⁻¹ (Stein & MacDonald 2004; Wegner et al. 2015), of which 0.42 % originate from the Yukon coast (assuming a total sediment flux of 1.8 Tg;

Couture et al. 2018). These numbers suggest that the Hg flux estimate of this study is consistent with sediment contributions and not unusually high, assuming a relatively uniform Hg distribution across the Arctic on average. The total Hg stock stored in YCP soils represents 0.023 % of the estimated $1,656 \pm 962$ Gg stored in the Northern Hemisphere permafrost region (Schuster et al. 2018). Assuming an approximate area of 600 km^2 for the Yukon coast (300 km coastline length with a terrain unit width of 2 km) and $20.8 \times 10^6 \text{ km}^2$ for the Northern Hemisphere permafrost region (Obu et al. 2019) results in 0.0029 % of the northern permafrost area being covered by the YCP—about ten times less than its relative Hg stock. This discrepancy may reflect strong regional variation of Hg accumulation and stocks or is due to estimation uncertainty. The high uncertainties in this study come from wide prediction intervals in model outcomes (Fig. 17), while uncertainties from sampling and measurements were mostly neglected in this study. Additionally, it is uncertain how well single-sample Hg concentrations represent Hg contents of entire terrain unit layers, given the likely heterogeneity within those layers. As data availability for the Yukon coast is very limited, this approach seemed the most appropriate. The relatively high local Hg stocks and the substantial uncertainties highlight the importance of spatially explicit, site-specific data. Improving regional estimates and reducing uncertainty in Hg budgets of regional studies will require more high-resolution data sets on Hg concentrations, erosion rates, and sediment characteristics along Arctic coasts.

Hg input into the Beaufort Sea from coastal erosion along the Yukon coast is minor compared to riverine input from the Mackenzie River but may differ in form and ecological relevance. The estimated annual Hg flux from coastal erosion from the Yukon coast represents only about 3.5 % of the Hg mass exported by the Mackenzie River, which contributes between 1,850 to 3,400 kg Hg annually (Emmerton et al. 2013; Mu et al. 2019). Despite this relatively small contribution, coastal erosion is a relevant Hg source due to its widespread pan-Arctic occurrence, distinct chemical characteristics of coastal permafrost material, spatio-temporal delivery dynamics, and potential bioavailability (Irrgang et al. 2022; Du et al. 2024). Riverine Hg is mostly particle-bound and sorbed to refractory OC (Zhang et al. 2015; Du et al. 2024). In the Arctic Ocean, this riverine Hg has been found to mostly increase surface ocean Hg concentrations in the nearshore zone, from where up to 80 % of the Hg evade back into the atmosphere (Zhang et al. 2015). In contrast, Hg released by coastal erosion

may be less strongly bound or even “matrix-free” due to abrupt thaw processes at the coast that rapidly expose and mobilize sediments (Du et al. 2024). This is consistent with the weak association between terrestrial Hg and TOC ($r = 0.14$, $p = 0.085$) or SSA ($r = -0.19$, $p = 0.18$) observed in this study, indicating a smaller particle-bound Hg fraction in coastal inputs. Biota near the Mackenzie River outflow exhibit low Hg levels, suggesting limited bioavailability of riverine Hg (Loseto et al. 2008). Seasonal dynamics further distinguish both sources. River discharge peaks during spring freshet in June and decreases throughout the summer, while coastal erosion can deliver Hg in irregular pulses linked to episodic events such as storms and concomitant wave attack (Barnhart et al. 2014; Yang et al. 2015), which peak during the sea-ice minimum in late summer (Atkinson 2005). Rivers are point sources of dissolved matter, but coastal erosion influences coastal ecosystems along the entire eroding coastline. All these contrasting input patterns underline the qualitative relevance of coastal erosion and affect transport, transformation and burial dynamics of Hg in the nearshore zone. While coastal erosion is not the dominant Hg source to the Beaufort Sea, it adds a qualitatively distinct and potentially ecologically significant Hg fraction to the marine environment.

7.2 Mercury in the terrestrial coastal domain

7.2.1 Terrestrial mercury concentrations in the Arctic context

The measured Hg concentrations from the Yukon coast showed typical Hg concentrations for an Arctic permafrost region. Analysis of 158 terrestrial samples revealed a mean Hg concentration of $79.07 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ with a range from $18.33 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ to $271.8 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. These values align with findings from Leitch (2006) who reported Hg concentrations ranging from 26 to $303 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ from five cores along the Canadian Beaufort Sea coast. Comparable levels were also found in a Central Yukon peatland (18 to $140 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$; Bandara et al. 2019), while a broader collection of 11,000 data by Schuster et al. (2018) showed a lower mean $36 \pm 37 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, and their own measurements from 588 different Alaskan soil samples averaged $62 \pm 35 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. Lower Hg concentrations were reported for deep permafrost in Yakutia averaging at $9.72 \pm 9.28 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (Rutkowski et al. 2021). High Hg concentrations up to $580 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ have been measured by Suleymanov et al. (2023) in an urban environment at

the city of Ufa, Russia. Critical thresholds of total Hg concentrations in soils for soil invertebrates were estimated between 25 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ in mineral soils, and 400 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ in organic soils (de Vries et al. 2002). Mahbub et al. (2018) found 600 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ as the *Hazardous Concentration 5%*, at which it is estimated that 95 % of the species in an environment are protected. Most Yukon coast sediment samples remained below critical thresholds, suggesting that, under current conditions, terrestrial Hg levels are unlikely to pose widespread risks to soil biota.

7.2.2 Spatial variability of mercury stocks

Hg concentrations and stocks varied considerably across the YCP, with highest values observed in the eastern part and on HIQ, caused by differences in glacial history, parent material, and hydrological regime. Significantly higher Hg concentrations occurred in the eastern part of the Yukon mainland coast, with a mean of $96.49 \pm 24.98 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, while concentrations in the western part were at $39.34 \pm 9.9 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. A similar pattern became obvious in Hg stocks (Fig. 22), with lowest stocks in sections 1 and 4 in the west which were least influenced by glacial processes. The western YCP remained unglaciated during the Last Glacial Maximum and consists of largely undisturbed, peat-rich lowlands with limited external sediment input, suggesting primarily atmospheric and geogenic Hg sources (Rampton 1982). In contrast, the eastern YCP underwent substantial glacial reworking in the late Pleistocene, likely incorporating heterogeneous parent material from marine and terrestrial deposits of varying origins and ages (Rampton 1982). These glacial processes could have contributed to higher Hg concentrations by redistributing and concentrating fine-grained sediments in moraine deposits. Recent thermokarst activity at the eastern mainland coast has formed today's landscape, with numerous lakes and wetlands which may alter Hg transportation, distribution and accumulation due to soil water movement with thawing permafrost, and dissolved OC-facilitated transport in local catchments (Grigal 2002; Giest et al. 2025). Extending this gradient, HIQ exhibits even higher mean Hg concentrations ($85.47 \pm 35.08 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) than the glaciated mainland coast, which may result from its more intense glacial history and the upthrust of marine sediments. While the mainland was reworked by the Laurentide Ice Sheet, HIQ was fully uplifted from the adjacent Herschel Basin and was reshaped by periglacial

processes (Mackay 1959). This caused a thorough mixing of sediments and incorporation of a wide variety of material types, including fine-textured marine sediments (Fritz et al. 2012) with higher Hg-binding capacity. The differences are confirmed by smaller mean grain sizes at HIQ than at the mainland, as shown in Figure 14 and also found by Fritz et al. (2012). The spatial patterns highlight the dominant role of geological history, sediment origin, and hydrological setting in shaping Hg distributions, demonstrating the importance of the geomorphological context when assessing potential Hg stocks across the Arctic.

Higher Hg concentrations occurred in the active layer than in underlying permafrost, most likely due to increased atmospheric Hg concentrations in the Anthropocene in combination with enhanced Hg uptake by plants from the atmosphere. On average, Hg concentrations in the active layer exceeded those in permafrost ($71.44 \pm 21.45 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) by an overall factor of 1.2, although the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.312$). This surficial enrichment pattern has been observed in multiple other Arctic studies, including Leitch (2006), Stern et al. (2012), Bandara et al. (2019), and Dastoor et al. (2022). Atmosphere and vegetation have been identified as key Hg sources for surface soils (Dastoor et al. 2022). Atmospheric Hg is deposited through both wet deposition and gaseous elemental mercury uptake by vegetation, which can account for up to 70 % of total deposition (Obrist et al. 2017). Increasing atmospheric Hg levels since the industrial revolution and the beginning of the Anthropocene have likely contributed to higher Hg uptake in surface layers (Driscoll et al. 2013; Bandara et al. 2019). The generally strong affinity of Hg to OM (Liao et al. 2009) and its mobility in soil water facilitate downward transport within the active layer (Bandara et al. 2019). In addition, cryoturbation—freeze-thaw driven mixing of soils—can relocate surficial material downward, redistributing Hg vertically and into the upper part of permafrost (Bockheim & Tarnocai 1998). An indication for cryoturbation is given by higher C/N ratios in permafrost than in surface layer samples, with the higher ratios in permafrost indicating less decomposed, more recent plant-derived terrestrial material (Lamb et al. 2006). Still, the observed difference in C/N ratios is unusual, and it remains unclear what drives this observation. A high degree of decomposition of fresh surficial material, which could also explain lower C/N ratios at the surface, is unlikely due to consistently elevated TOC contents in those samples. Cryoturbation might contribute to the lack of a statistically significant

difference in Hg concentrations between active layer and permafrost by mixing Hg-enriched surface material into deeper layers. Additionally, post-depositional re-emission may reduce net surface accumulation: Arctic soils and vegetation are estimated to re-emit about 24,000 (7,000-59,000) kg Hg per year, roughly one-fifth of total atmospheric deposition (Dastoor et al. 2022). Despite slightly higher concentrations in surface layers, only 6.1 % of the total Hg mass were stored in the top one meter of YCP sediments. The bulk Hg mass was stored in deeper permafrost layers, especially within high bluffs exceeding 20 m, making them the dominant source of Hg to the Arctic Ocean as permafrost thaw and erosion intensify. The vertical distribution highlights the importance of considering both Hg concentrations and released sediment volume when assessing potential Hg input into Arctic coastal systems.

7.2.3 Drivers of mercury fluxes from coastal erosion

When normalized to eroded volume, Hg stocks were the primary control by nature on Hg fluxes, not bluff height or erosion rate. To assess whether Hg release was primarily driven by Hg stocks or by the volume of eroded sediment, linear correlations and multiple linear regressions were examined across three scales: fluxes per cubic meter, fluxes per meter of shoreline, and total fluxes per terrain unit. Fluxes per cubic meter of eroded material were highest from HIQ and the eastern YCP, reflecting elevated sediment Hg concentrations in these areas. Across terrain units, there was a strong correlation with Hg stocks per cubic meter ($r = 0.63$, $p < 0.001$). A multiple linear regression—performed to examine the relevance of Hg stocks, bluff height, and erosion rate on Hg fluxes—confirmed the major relevance of Hg stock per cubic meter, which was the only significant predictor of flux per cubic meter ($p < 0.001$). In contrast, fluxes per meter of coastline were more strongly associated with physical erosion parameters. According to the multiple linear regression, bluff height ($p < 0.001$) and erosion rate ($p < 0.001$) were the significant predictors. A similar pattern emerged for total Hg fluxes per terrain unit, which correlated with total Hg stocks per terrain unit ($r = 0.58$, $p < 0.001$) and their bluff height ($r = 0.59$, $p < 0.001$). The multiple regression identified bluff height ($p = 0.003$) and area eroded ($p = 0.003$) as significant predictors, suggesting that Hg stocks play a secondary role at this scale. These calculations indicate that volumetric Hg stocks

determine the order of magnitude of Hg release per unit volume of eroded sediment, while absolute and shoreline-normalized fluxes are primarily shaped by the physical drivers of erosion (bluff height, change rate, and area eroded). Areas with low soil Hg concentrations may contribute substantially to overall Hg release if erosion volumes are high, which emphasizes the need to account for geomorphological dynamics in contaminant flux and risk assessments.

7.3 Fate of mercury in the marine environment

Hg distribution in marine sediment samples showed no consistent pattern within 500 m off the Yukon coast, suggesting that this nearshore zone is too narrow or dynamic to reveal a consistent trend in sedimentary Hg concentrations. The correlation between Hg concentration and distance to shore in this zone was weak and not statistically significant ($r = 0.15$, $p = 0.2$). Marine sediments here show no systematic trend in the terrigenous component with increasing distance from shore (Couture et al. 2018), indicating that sediment and associated Hg derived from coastal erosion is not predominantly deposited in the immediate nearshore zone. Elevated Hg concentrations reported beyond the shelf break suggest long-range transport of particle-bound Hg, likely facilitated by fine particles with high Hg affinity that remain in suspension over long distances (Schwarzkopf 2023). The offshore burial of particle-bound Hg in deeper offshore sediments beyond the shelf break highlights the limited role of the nearshore zone as a long-term sink and suggests that the fate of eroded Hg is strongly influenced by transport dynamics.

Lower Hg concentrations in marine sediments compared to terrestrial material suggest that a substantial fraction of Hg released from coastal erosion is not retained on the sea floor. Mercury levels in marine sediments showed significantly lower mean Hg concentrations ($52.04 \pm 27.93 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) than the average terrestrial sample ($74.52 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), consistent with findings by Braune et al. (2015), Bełdowska et al. (2016), Kwasigroch et al. (2018), and Giest et al. (2025). This likely reflects not only offshore transport but also biological uptake, Hg dissolution in sea water, and gaseous exchange with the atmosphere. Nearshore zones are areas of high biological activity due to low water depths and nutrient inputs from coasts and rivers (Terhaar et al. 2021). In such settings, Hg remaining in the water column—

especially in its methylated form—is more relevant for phytoplankton and marine biota than Hg buried in sediments (Jonsson et al. 2022). Despite the proximity to the Mackenzie Delta, eastern YCP sediments did not show elevated Hg levels, indicating that either sediment deposition from the plume is limited or that the material is rapidly transported into other areas. In addition to the lateral transport, ocean-atmosphere exchange continuously modifies Hg concentrations in surface waters, with a net flux from sea to air and sea-ice cover limiting this process seasonally (Dastoor et al. 2022). The multiple transformation and transportation pathways of Hg in the water column are complex and can vary locally (Braune et al. 2015). This complexity complicates source attribution and raises concern that Hg and especially MeHg could increasingly enter Arctic food webs.

The spatial distribution of marine sediment Hg concentrations showed a different pattern than the terrestrial sediment Hg concentrations, suggesting that lateral transport and regional coastal processes shape Hg distribution along the Beaufort coast. No linear correlation was found between terrestrial Hg fluxes and Hg concentrations in adjacent marine nearshore sediments from the same terrain unit ($r = -0.19$, $p = 0.54$), indicating that high terrestrial input does not directly translate into elevated marine Hg concentrations within the first 500 m offshore which is supported by Hg measurement of Petzold (2024). The spatial pattern of elevated terrestrial Hg concentrations on HIQ and at the eastern mainland coast, however, was reflected in adjacent marine sediments. This points to the influence of winds, coastal currents, and sediment resuspension (Gimsa et al. 2024). The Beaufort Undercurrent, flowing from west to east along the mainland shore, could transport coastal material towards the Mackenzie Delta, while freshwater inputs from smaller rivers of the YCP influence surficial currents and sediment transport locally. Transformations, resuspension and particle association in the water column further influence the regional fate of Hg. As a result, marine Hg inventories cannot be inferred directly from terrestrial source data without taking nearshore dynamics into account.

7.4 Methylmercury—transformations, pathways, potential risk

7.4.1 Spatial patterns and environmental controls on methylmercury

MeHg concentrations in sediments of the YCP were low and within typical ranges for Arctic terrestrial and nearshore environments. Terrestrial MeHg concentrations ranged from $0.064 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ to $1.24 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, with a mean of $0.29 \pm 0.25 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. This is comparable to values reported for other Arctic soils (Jonsson et al. 2022), and substantially lower than peak levels of $6.7 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ found in Arctic wetland soils (Varty et al. 2021). Marine sediment MeHg levels were even lower, ranging from $0.08 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ to $0.38 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, consistent with measurement by Fox et al. (2014), who reported a mean value of $0.37 \pm 0.36 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ in nearshore Beaufort Sea sediments. In both marine and terrestrial samples, %MeHg was low, ranging from 0.07 to 2.85 %. Such low percentages are typical in sediments, but are in strong contrast to marine biota, where MeHg can constitute up to 99 % of total Hg (Loseto et al. 2008). No critical thresholds for MeHg concentrations in soils exist, but the Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment (CCME) gave a threshold of $6,600 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for total Hg in agricultural and residential soils (CCME 1999). If about one percent of this (assuming %MeHg = 1 % = $66 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) would be a critical threshold for MeHg, sediment concentrations of the Yukon coast would clearly stay below this threshold. Higher Hg delivery through atmospheric deposition, permafrost thawing, and coastal erosion could increase MeHg stocks in soils of the Yukon coast, but it seems unlikely that this would result in concerningly high concentrations in soils.

MeHg concentrations increased from permafrost to active layer to mud pools, and declined slightly in thaw stream sediments, reflecting the progression from frozen, low-activity soils to water-saturated zones. Intact permafrost showed low MeHg concentrations ($0.17 \pm 0.11 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), consistent with limited microbial activity under frozen conditions (Rivkina et al. 2004). Higher MeHg levels were measured in active layer samples ($0.55 \pm 0.37 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 8$), where seasonal thaw allows for microbial activity. The underlying permafrost acts as a barrier for vertical water transport, restricting drainage and potentially creating favorable conditions for anaerobic microbes known to mediate Hg methylation (Bravo & Cosio 2020). Mud pools, located at the base of RTS headwalls and cliffs, probably provided the most anoxic environments due to persistent waterlogging caused by ice melting and limited drainage (Blodau 2002). MeHg concentrations were elevated here, with a mean of

$0.41 \pm 0.32 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ ($n = 9$), which could be reflected by anaerobic conditions that drive microbial Hg methylation (Jonsson et al. 2022; Cardinal et al. 2025). Sediments in thaw streams that transport material from mud pools into the ocean showed lower MeHg levels ($0.27 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, $n = 3$), suggesting that oxic conditions in the streams could promote demethylation (Ullrich et al. 2001). These patterns are derived from 46 samples which may not fully represent their respective landforms. It is unclear how stable MeHg concentrations in these environments are and how quickly methylation and demethylation processes alter MeHg sediment concentrations (Baptista-Salazar et al. 2022; Jonsson et al. 2022; Fabre et al. 2024). A significant part of MeHg can be stored in refractory pools, meaning it is not readily available for demethylation. This has been observed for sediments from lakes and brackish seawater sites, as well as soils from forests and marsh environments (Baptista-Salazar et al. 2022). When this happens in mud pools or wetlands (known for promoting MeHg formation), MeHg could be protected from demethylation during transport into other environments (Baptista-Salazar et al. 2022). It remains unknown how large the refractory pool in our samples is, so that the measurements of this study might represent a temporal snapshot rather than stable background levels. Factors such as temperature, OM availability and quality, and discharge variability may influence short-term MeHg dynamics outside of refractory pools (Schartup et al. 2015; Z. Yang et al. 2016; Seelen et al. 2023). Hydrological regime and redox conditions seem to influence MeHg distribution in bluffs and RTSs, but the interplay of production, transformation, and transport processes is complex, and measured concentrations likely reflect transient conditions rather than steady-state behavior.

7.4.2 Nearshore methylmercury dynamics

MeHg concentrations in marine sediments increased with distance from shore and were strongly related to TOC and SSA distribution. Nearshore sediments within the first 500 m from shore were mostly sandy, and silt content increased with distance from shore, similar to findings from Gimsa et al. (2024). This distribution reflects wave-induced winnowing in the very nearshore zone, with finer particles with higher SSA staying in suspension over longer distances. TOC contents of marine sediments were generally low ($< 3\%$) but increased with distance from shore ($r =$

0.7, $p < 0.001$). This TOC distribution is consistent with the resuspension and deposition zones classified by Jong et al. (2020), who found that terrestrial carbon is mostly deposited in the deposition zone beyond the first few hundred meters offshore. Marine sediment MeHg content rose from $0.08 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (beach) to a maximum of $0.38 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (800 m offshore) and was strongly correlated with TOC ($r = 0.89$, $p < 0.001$) and SSA ($r = 0.74$, $p < 0.001$). Two mechanisms could drive this offshore increase and explain the strong correlations:

(1) Particle-bound MeHg produced in terrestrial sediments is carried offshore with fine, organic-rich particles and settles before extensive water-column transformation takes place.

(2) High SSA and TOC content provide substrates and microenvironments conducive to microbial Hg methylation at the sea floor.

Generally, the MeHg production in marine sediments can be reduced compared to production in terrestrial sediments (Lehnherr 2014). There are several possible pathways and processes that influence MeHg content in the nearshore zone: coastal erosion releases mostly Hg(II) which can be methylated in reducing zones (Hollweg et al. 2010; Lehnherr et al. 2011; Dastoor et al. 2022). Storm-induced wave attacks cause rapid erosion events and introduce episodic, high-intensity sediment inputs to the ocean along the Alaskan Beaufort Sea coast (Barnhart et al. 2014). These pulse events can temporarily raise Hg concentrations in coastal waters by a factor of 10 to 30 (found at cliffs of the Polish Baltic shore; Beldowska et al. 2016), potentially increasing MeHg production and uptake by primary producers in biologically active zones. Given the complexity of sediment transport and redox dynamics, it remains challenging to distinguish the contributions of terrestrial inputs from local MeHg production in the Arctic Ocean.

Marine sediments exhibited a strong positive correlation between Hg and MeHg concentrations, in contrast to weak and variable relationships in terrestrial sediments, suggesting more consistent or simplified controls on MeHg content in marine settings than on land. In marine sediments, Hg and MeHg concentrations were significantly correlated ($r = 0.69$, $p < 0.001$), showing that areas with higher Hg levels tend to support higher MeHg concentrations. This pattern could reflect a relatively uniform depositional environment with stable redox conditions and fine and organic-rich particles that simplify controls on MeHg production (Lehnherr et

al. 2012; Cossa et al. 2014). In contrast, terrestrial sediments showed no significant Hg-MeHg correlation ($r = -0.14, p = 0.33$) and lacked significant correlations with TOC ($p = -0.04, r = 0.77$) and SSA ($r = 0.08, p = 0.58$). The weak correlations reflect the heterogeneous mosaic of soil moisture regimes, OM quality, redox conditions, and microbial communities on land (Lehnherr et al. 2012; Tarbier et al. 2021; Cardinal et al. 2025), as terrestrial samples originated from different landforms (active layer, permafrost, RTS floor). Though direct comparisons are missing, similar differences in correlation patterns under marine and terrestrial conditions can be derived from other studies. Liu et al. (2015) found positive correlations of MeHg with TOC and TN for marine sediments from Kongsfjorden, Svalbard, while correlations of MeHg with TOC and Hg in freshwater lake sediments in Ny-Ålesund were not found (Gopikrishna et al. 2020). Tighter Hg-MeHg coupling in marine sediments implies that marine MeHg concentrations may be more readily predicted from Hg inputs alone, whereas identifying terrestrial MeHg hotspots will require high-resolution environmental data to capture multiple interacting controls.

7.4.3 Potential risks and implications for Arctic food webs

Current MeHg concentrations in terrestrial and marine sediments do not indicate a direct risk to the local population or wildlife, but potential impacts through bioaccumulation in the food web cannot be excluded. Measured MeHg levels were not elevated compared to other Arctic regions which suggests no exceptional processes are occurring in soils at the Yukon coast. However, low sedimentary values are not indicative of ecological or human health risks and offer limited insight into actual MeHg dynamics (Ullrich et al. 2001; Fox et al. 2014). Arctic vegetation, particularly mosses and lichens, commonly bioaccumulate MeHg to levels two orders of magnitude higher than in underlying soils (e.g., median MeHg concentration of $0.18 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ in soils, and $66.8 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ in lichens; St. Pierre et al. 2015), providing a pathway into terrestrial food webs. Caribou, which consume large amounts of lichen, can ingest significant MeHg loads, even though their kidney tissue has not shown elevated levels with Hg concentrations up to $6.2 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$, of which 75 to 90 % is MeHg (Gamberg et al. 2015). The marine food web is more prone to bioaccumulation as the water column has been identified as an effective place for methylation, accounting for 47 ± 62 % of MeHg formation from inorganic Hg(II)

in polar marine waters (Lehnherr et al. 2011). Additionally, the number of steps in the marine food web is higher than on land, providing more levels of Hg biomagnification (Cohen 1994; Gamberg et al. 2015). St. Pierre et al. (2018) reported a strong increase in MeHg water concentrations of two orders of magnitude from discharge of an RTS. Together with benthic-pelagic coupling (where sediment-derived MeHg is remobilized into overlying waters through resuspension of sediment-bound MeHg), water-column methylation and discharged RTS water supply MeHg to phytoplankton (Kirk et al. 2012). Beginning in phytoplankton, MeHg bioaccumulates and biomagnifies in zooplankton, fish, and marine mammals (Watras et al. 1998; Campbell et al. 2005), while the latter are key subsistence species for Indigenous Peoples (AMAP 2021). Neither water-column MeHg nor MeHg levels in marine biota were measured in this study, pointing to an integrated water-sediment-biota analysis in a next step, including seasonal water-column profiles and fish tissue sampling. With rising Hg inputs from increasing coastal erosion, long-term monitoring programs for MeHg levels in water, phytoplankton, zooplankton, benthos, and fish tissues are needed to anticipate and mitigate future risks to Arctic food security.

7.5 Mercury in the One Health framework

With ongoing climate warming, it becomes increasingly important to address the interconnectedness of environmental, animal, and human health in a One Health framework (Fig. 26). Hg in a changing Arctic is a powerful example of how these systems interact: human-induced climate warming and increased Hg emissions from coal combustion and gold mining lead to enriched Hg stocks in Arctic soils, which are increasingly mobilized by permafrost thaw and coastal erosion (AMAP 2021; IPCC 2022). The previously frozen as well as the deposited atmospheric Hg is mobilized and released into aquatic and marine systems, where it may be transformed into MeHg, depending on Hg availability, redox conditions, and microbial activity (Ullrich et al. 2001; Lehnherr et al. 2011). This MeHg accumulates in fish and marine mammals, many of which are central to the diets, traditions, and well-being of Indigenous Peoples in the Arctic (AMAP 2021). Therefore, protecting environmental systems such as permafrost is not only a matter of ecosystem and landscape preservation, but is also directly linked to animal and human health.

Figure 26: The One Health framework in the Arctic (from Westerveld et al. 2023).

This study quantified Hg stocks and fluxes originating from the erosion of the Yukon coast, and provides important baseline data on Hg inputs from terrestrial sources. Significant knowledge gaps remain in understanding the complete picture of Hg cycling in the region. In particular, other fluxes such as atmospheric deposition, material transport via rivers and ocean currents, and biotic interactions have not been quantified and characterized so far. Future research should focus on MeHg concentrations, exposures, and transformation pathways, which will require high-resolution sampling of soils, vegetation, and biota, potentially during different seasons. Integrating Indigenous Knowledge through community engagement and two-way knowledge exchange not only improves study set-up and scientific understanding but also ensures relevance, acceptance, and accountability of the findings (Houde et al. 2022). Indigenous Knowledge has always been a holistic approach, including entire systems, and the concept of One Health is increasingly integrated into conservative research efforts. This study contributes to the One Health framework by providing data on environmental Hg occurrences and

processes, building a foundation for further assessments on its effects on animal and human health in the Yukon coastal region. A comprehensive, interdisciplinary, and inclusive research approach is needed to fully comply to the One Health framework.

8 Conclusion

This study aimed to quantify Hg stocks and fluxes along the Yukon coast, a region characterized by ongoing coastal erosion driven by permafrost thaw and increased wave action, with erosion rates reaching up to 22 m per year. To estimate Hg stocks and fluxes, sediment concentrations were determined using a combination of measurements from terrestrial and marine sediment samples as well as predictive modeling with a random forest algorithm. The obtained Hg concentrations were combined with sediment volume and observed erosion rates to calculate total and local stock and flux estimates. MeHg concentrations were analyzed for certain samples and compared across different landforms and along a marine transect in front of an RTS.

Measured and modeled Hg concentrations were within typical ranges for the Arctic permafrost environments and clearly remained below the critical thresholds of $6,600 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ given by the CCME for agricultural and residential soils (CCME 1999). Based on collected Hg concentrations, a total Hg stock of 381,080 kg (271,540 to 501,930 kg) was estimated for the YCP, with approximately 113 kg (87 to 163 kg) released into the Arctic Ocean annually due to coastal erosion.

The magnitude of Hg release alone does not reflect the environmental relevance it may pose. The fate of Hg in the marine environment depends on its transport, transformation, and potential bioavailability. This study supports previous findings that a certain fraction of the eroded Hg is likely transported beyond the nearshore zone, may evade into the atmosphere, or bioaccumulate in marine food webs, as marine sediments showed lower Hg concentrations than terrestrial soil. Of particular concern is how much Hg is converted into the neurotoxic MeHg in the water column, which bioaccumulates in the food web.

Although MeHg concentrations in both terrestrial and marine sediments were low, sediment data alone are insufficient to characterize MeHg dynamics in the broader marine environment. Consequently, this study does not allow for distinct conclusions regarding the risk to local communities from MeHg exposure through sea food consumption. No elevated MeHg levels in sediments were found, which suggests no unusual methylation activity in the immediate coastal zone.

Future research should focus on expanded soil sampling along the Yukon coast to refine stock and flux estimates and reduce current uncertainties. However, more critical is to put efforts on quantifying MeHg concentrations in sea water and in key species consumed by Indigenous Peoples in the region, as these pathways are most relevant for ensuring human and ecological health.

9 References

- Aagaard, K. (1984). The Beaufort Undercurrent. In P. W. Barnes, D. M. Schell & E. Reimnitz (eds.), *The Alaskan Beaufort Sea: Ecosystems and Environments* (1. edition). Academic Press.
- Alexeeva, N. V. & Erbajeva, M. A. (2000). Pleistocene permafrost in Western Transbaikalia. *Quaternary International* **68-71**, 5–12.
- AMAP (2015). *AMAP Assessment 2015: Human Health in the Arctic*. Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP).
- AMAP (2021). *AMAP Assessment 2021: Mercury in the Arctic*. Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP).
- Anthony, E. J. (1989). Chenier plain development in northern Sierra Leone, West Africa. *Marine Geology* **90**, 297–309. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227\(89\)90132-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-3227(89)90132-1)
- Aré, F. E. (1988). Thermal abrasion of sea coasts (part I). *Polar Geography and Geology* **12**(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10889378809377343>
- Atkinson, D. E. (2005). Observed storminess patterns and trends in the circum-Arctic coastal regime. *Geo-Marine Letters* **25**(2-3), 98–109. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00367-004-0191-0>
- Bandara, S., Froese, D. G., Louis, V. L. S., Cooke, C. A. & Calmels, F. (2019). Postdepositional Mercury Mobility in a Permafrost Peatland from Central Yukon, Canada. *ACS Earth and Space Chemistry* **3**(5), 770–778. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsearthspacechem.9b00010>
- Baptista-Salazar, C., van Liem-Nguyen & Jonsson, S. (2022). Experiments revealing the formation of refractory methylmercury pools in natural sediments and soils. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* **328**, 76–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gca.2022.04.009>
- Barnhart, K. R., Anderson, R. S., Overeem, I., Wobus, C., Clow, G. D. & Urban, F. E. (2014). Modeling erosion of ice-rich permafrost bluffs along the Alaskan Beaufort Sea coast. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface* **119**(5), 1155–1179. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2013JF002845>
- Bartsch, A., Widhalm, B., Pointner, G., Ermokhina, K. A., Leibman, M. & Heim, B. (2019). *Landcover derived from Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellite data (2015-2018) for subarctic and arctic environments [dataset]*. Zentralanstalt für Meteorologie und Geodynamik, Wien. <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.897916>*, last checked on 29. June 2025
- Beldowska, M., Jędruch, A., Łęczyński, L., Saniewska, D. & Kwasigroch, U. (2016). Coastal erosion as a source of mercury into the marine environment along the Polish Baltic shore. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* **23**(16), 16372–16382. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-016-6753-7>
- Berry, G. (1986). Statistical significance and confidence intervals. *Medical Journal of Australia* **144**(12), 618–619. <https://doi.org/10.5694/j.1326-5377.1986.tb112339.x>
- Bishop, K., Shanley, J. B., Riscassi, A., Wit, H. A. d., Eklöf, K., Meng, B., Mitchell, C., Osterwalder, S., Schuster, P. F., Webster, J. & Zhu, W. (2020). Recent advances in understanding and measurement of mercury in the environment: Terrestrial Hg cycling. *Science of the Total Environment* **721**, 137647. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.137647>
- Biskaborn, B. K., Smith, S. L., Noetzi, J., Matthes, H., Vieira, G., Streletskiy, D. A., Schoeneich, P., Romanovsky, V. E., Lewkowicz, A. G., Abramov, A., Allard, M., Boike, J., Cable, W. L., Christiansen, H. H., Delaloye, R., Diekmann, B., Drozdov, D., Etzelmüller, B., Grosse, G., et al., Lantuit, H. (2019). Permafrost is warming at a global scale. *Nature Communications* **10**(1), 264. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-08240-4>
- Blodau, C. (2002). Carbon cycling in peatlands - A review of processes and controls. *Environmental Reviews* **10**(2), 111–134. <https://doi.org/10.1139/a02-004>
- Blott, S. & Pye, K. (2001). GRADISTAT: A grain size distribution and statistics package for the analysis of unconsolidated sediments. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* **26**, 1237–1248. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.261>
- Bockheim, J. G. & Tarnocai, C. (1998). Recognition of cryoturbation for classifying permafrost-affected soils. *Geoderma* **81**, 281–293. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061\(97\)00115-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-7061(97)00115-8)

- Braune, B., Chételat, J., Amyot, M., Brown, T., Clayden, M., Evans, M., Fisk, A., Gaden, A., Girard, C., Hare, A., Kirk, J., Lehnherr, I., Letcher, R., Loseto, L., Macdonald, R., Mann, E., McMeans, B., Muir, D., O'Driscoll, N., et al., Stern, G. (2015). Mercury in the marine environment of the Canadian Arctic: Review of recent findings. *Science of the Total Environment* **509-510**, 67–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2014.05.133>
- Bravo, A. G. & Cosio, C. (2020). Biotic formation of methylmercury: A bio–physico–chemical conundrum. *Limnology and Oceanography* **65**(5), 1010–1027. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lno.11366>
- Breiman, L. (2001). Random Forests. *Machine Learning* **45**.
- Brembach, K., Pleskachevsky, A. & Lantuit, H. (2023). Investigating High-Resolution Spatial Wave Patterns on the Canadian Beaufort Shelf Using Synthetic Aperture Radar Imagery at Herschel Island, Qikiqtaruk, Yukon, Canada. *Remote Sensing* **15**(19). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15194753>
- Brigatti, M. F., Colonna, S., Malferrari, D., Medici, L. & Poppi, L. (2005). Mercury adsorption by montmorillonite and vermiculite: A combined XRD, TG-MS, and EXAFS study. *Applied Clay Science* **28**(1-4 SPEC. ISS), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clay.2004.03.006>
- Bringloe, T. T., Wilkinson, D. P., Goldsmit, J., Savoie, A. M., Filbee-Dexter, K., Macgregor, K. A., Howland, K. L., McKindsey, C. W. & Verbruggen, H. (2022). Arctic marine forest distribution models showcase potentially severe habitat losses for cryophilic species under climate change. *Global Change Biology* **28**(11), 3711–3727. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16142>
- Burn, C. R. (2009). After whom is herschel island named? *Arctic* **62**(3), 317–323. <https://doi.org/10.14430/arctic152>
- Burn, C. R. & Zhang, Y. (2009). Permafrost and climate change at Herschel Island (Qikiqtaruk), Yukon Territory, Canada. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface* **114**(2). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008JF001087>
- Campbell, L. M., Norstrom, R. J., Hobson, K. A., Muir, D. C. G., Backus, S. & Fisk, A. T. (2005). Mercury and other trace elements in a pelagic Arctic marine food web (Northwater Polynya, Baffin Bay). *Science of the Total Environment* **351-352**, 247–263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2005.02.043>
- Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment [CCME] (1999). *Mercury - Soil Quality Guidelines for the Protection of Environmental and Human Health*. https://ccme.ca/en/chemical/131*, last checked on 29. June 2025
- Cardinal, R. M., Roy-Léveillé, P., Gauthier, S. & Branfireun, B. (2025). Methylmercury concentrations in a degrading lithalsa field: Effects of thermokarst development and revegetation. *Science of the Total Environment* **976**, 179276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.179276>
- Chakraborty, P., Sharma, B., Babu, P. V. R., Yao, K. M. & Jaychandran, S. (2014). Impact of total organic carbon (in sediments) and dissolved organic carbon (in overlying water column) on Hg sequestration by coastal sediments from the central east coast of India. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* **79**(1-2), 342–347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2013.11.028>
- Chételat, J., McKinney, M. A., Amyot, M., Dastoor, A., Douglas, T. A., Heimbürger-Boavida, L. E., Kirk, J., Kahilainen, K. K., Outridge, P. M., Pelletier, N., Skov, H., St. Pierre, K. A., Vuorenmaa, J. & Wang, F. (2022). Climate change and mercury in the Arctic: Abiotic interactions. *Science of the Total Environment* **824**, 153715. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2022.153715>
- Clarkson, T. W. (1992). Mercury: Major Issues in Environmental Health. *Environmental Health Perspectives* **100**, 31–38. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.9310031>
- Cohen, J. E. (1994). Marine and continental food webs: three paradoxes? *Philosophical Transactions - Royal Society of London, B* **343**(1303), 57–69. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.1994.0008>
- Cossa, D., Garnier, C., Buscail, R., Elbaz-Poulichet, F., Mikac, N., Patel-Sorrentino, N., Tessier, E., Rigaud, S., Lenoble, V. & Gobeil, C. (2014). A Michaelis-Menten type equation for describing methylmercury dependence on inorganic mercury in aquatic sediments. *Biogeochemistry* **119**(1-3), 35–43. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-013-9924-3>
- Couture, N. J., Irrgang, A. M., Pollard, W., Lantuit, H. & Fritz, M. (2018). Coastal Erosion of Permafrost Soils Along the Yukon Coastal Plain and Fluxes of Organic Carbon to the Canadian Beaufort Sea. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Biogeosciences* **123**(2), 406–422. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017JG004166>

- Dastoor, A., Angot, H., Bieser, J., Christensen, J. H., Douglas, T. A., Heimbürger-Boavida, L. E., Jiskra, M., Mason, R. P., McLagan, D. S., Obrist, D., Outridge, P. M., Petrova, M. V., Ryjkov, A., St. Pierre, K. A., Schartup, A. T., Soerensen, A. L., Toyota, K., Travnikov, O., Wilson, S. J. & Zdanowicz, C. (2022). Arctic mercury cycling. *Nature Reviews Earth and Environment* **3**(4), 270–286. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-022-00269-w>
- de Vries, W., Schütze, G., Lots, S., Meili, M., Römkens, P., Farret, R., de Temmerman, L. & Jakubowski, M. (2002). *Critical limits for cadmium, lead and mercury related to ecotoxicological effects on soil organisms, aquatic organisms, plants, animals and humans*. UN-ECE Convention on long range transboundary air pollution.
- Dietz, R., Sonne, C., Basu, N., Braune, B., O'Hara, T., Letcher, R. J., Scheuhammer, T., Andersen, M., Andreasen, C., Andriashek, D., Asmund, G., Aubail, A., Baagøe, H., Born, E. W., Chan, H. M., Derocher, A. E., Grandjean, P., Knott, K., Kirkegaard, M., et al., Aars, J. (2013). What are the toxicological effects of mercury in Arctic biota? *Science of the Total Environment* **443**, 775–790. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2012.11.046>
- Donaldson, S. G., van Oostdam, J., Tikhonov, C., Feeley, M., Armstrong, B., Ayotte, P., Boucher, O., Bowers, W., Chan, L., Dallaire, F., Dallaire, R., Dewailly, É., Edwards, J., Egeland, G. M., Fontaine, J., Furgal, C., Leech, T., Loring, E., Muckle, G., et al., Shearer, R. G. (2010). Environmental contaminants and human health in the Canadian Arctic. *Science of the Total Environment* **408**(22), 5165–5234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2010.04.059>
- Douglas, T. A., Loseto, L. L., MacDonald, R. W., Outridge, P., Dommergue, A., Poulain, A., Amyot, M., Barkay, T., Berg, T., Chetelat, J., Constant, P., Evans, M., Ferrari, C., Gantner, N., Johnson, M. S., Kirk, J., Kroer, N., Larose, C., Lean, D., et al., Zdanowicz, C. M. (2012). The fate of mercury in Arctic terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, a review. *Environmental Chemistry* **9**(4), 321–355. <https://doi.org/10.1071/EN11140>
- Driscoll, C. T., Mason, R. P., Chan, H. M., Jacob, D. J. & Pirrone, N. (2013). Mercury as a global pollutant: Sources, pathways, and effects. *Environmental Science and Technology* **47**(10), 4967–4983. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es305071v>
- Du, J., Hu, L., Yao, Z., Liu, X., Sun, Y., Yang, G., Aksentov, K., Vasilenko, Y., Bosin, A., Astakhov, A. & Shi, X. (2024). Terrestrial input and biological processes drive varying mineral/organic matrix-related mercury sequestration and deposition in the East Siberian Arctic Shelf. *Chemical Geology* **670**, 122409. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2024.122409>
- Ehlers, J., Gibbard, P. L. & Hughes, P. D. (2011). *Quaternary Glaciations - Extent and Chronology: A Closer Look* (15. edition). Elsevier.
- Emmerton, C. A., Graydon, J. A., Gareis, J. A. L., St. Louis, V. L., Lesack, L. F. W., Banack, J. K. A., Hicks, F. & Nafziger, J. (2013). Mercury export to the Arctic Ocean from the Mackenzie River, Canada. *Environmental Science and Technology* **47**(14), 7644–7654. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es400715r>
- Environment & Climate Change Canada [ECCC] (2025). *Canadian Climate Normals 1991-2020 Data - Komakuk Beach*. https://climate.weather.gc.ca/climate_normals/index_e.html*, last checked on 29. June 2025
- Fabre, C., Sonke, J. E., Tananaev, N. & Teisserenc, R. (2024). Organic carbon and mercury exports from pan-Arctic rivers in a thawing permafrost context – A review. *Science of the Total Environment* **954**, 176713. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.176713>
- Falardeau, J., Vernal, A. d., Fréchette, B., Hillaire-Marcel, C., Archambault, P., Fritz, M., Gallagher, C. P. & Tanski, G. (2023). Impacts of stronger winds and less sea ice on Canadian Beaufort Sea shelf ecosystems since the late 1990s. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* **294**, 108520. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2023.108520>
- Fox, A. L., Hughes, E. A., Trocine, R. P., Trefry, J. H., Schonberg, S. V., McTigue, N. D., Lasorsa, B. K., Konar, B. & Cooper, L. W. (2014). Mercury in the northeastern Chukchi Sea: Distribution patterns in seawater and sediments and biomagnification in the benthic food web. *Deep-Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* **102**, 56–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.DSR2.2013.07.012>
- Fox, J. & Weisberg, S. (2019). *An R Companion to Applied Regression* (3. edition). SAGE Publications, Inc.

- French, H. M. (2007). *The Periglacial Environment* (3. edition). Wiley.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118684931>
- Friedlingstein, P., Bopp, L., Ciais, P., Dufresne, J. L., Fairhead, L., LeTreut, H., Monfray, P. & Orr, J. (2001). Positive feedback between future climate change and the carbon cycle. *Geophysical Research Letters* **28**(8), 1543–1546. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2000GL012015>
- Fritz, M., Vonk, J. E. & Lantuit, H. (2017). Collapsing Arctic coastlines. *Nature Climate Change* **7**, 6–7. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate3188>
- Fritz, M., Wetterich, S., Meyer, H., Schirrmeyer, L., Lantuit, H. & Pollard, W. H. (2011). Origin and characteristics of massive ground ice on Herschel Island (western Canadian Arctic) as revealed by stable water isotope and Hydrochemical signatures. *Permafrost and Periglacial Processes* **22**(1), 26–38. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppp.714>
- Fritz, M., Wetterich, S., Schirrmeyer, L., Meyer, H., Lantuit, H., Preusser, F. & Pollard, W. H. (2012). Eastern Beringia and beyond: Late Wisconsinan and Holocene landscape dynamics along the Yukon Coastal Plain, Canada. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* **319-320**, 28–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PALAEO.2011.12.015>
- Fukumori, I., Wang, O. & Fenty, I. (2021). Causal Mechanisms of Sea Level and Freshwater Content Change in the Beaufort Sea. *Journal of Physical Oceanography* **51**(10), 3217–3234. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JPO-D-21-0069.1>
- Gamberg, M., Chételat, J., Poulain, A. J., Zdanowicz, C. & Zheng, J. (2015). Mercury in the Canadian Arctic Terrestrial Environment: An Update. *Science of the Total Environment* **509-510**, 28–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.04.070>
- Giest, F. P., Jenrich, M., Grosse, G., Jones, B. M., Mangelsdorf, K., Windirsch, T. & Strauss, J. (2025). Organic carbon, mercury, and sediment characteristics along a land–shore transect in Arctic Alaska. *Biogeosciences* **22**(12), 2871–2887. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-22-2871-2025>
- Gimsa, J., Fritz, M. & Lantuit, H. (2024). Nearshore Hydrodynamics and Sediment Dispersal Along Eroding Permafrost Coasts—Insights From Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler Measurements Around Herschel Island—Qikiqtaruk (Yukon, Canada). *Permafrost and Periglacial Processes* **36**(2). <https://doi.org/10.1002/ppp.2258>
- Gopikrishna, V. G., Kannan, V. M., Binish, M. B., Shukkur, M. A., Krishnan, K. P. & Mohan, M. (2020). Mercury in the sediments of freshwater lakes in Ny-Ålesund, Arctic. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* **192**(8). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-020-08511-y>
- Government of Canada (2025). *Conserved areas*. https://indicators-map.canada.ca/App/Data?id=Conserved_Areas&GoCTemplateCulture=en-CA*, last checked on 29. June 2025
- Grandjean, P., Satoh, H., Murata, K. & Eto, K. (2010). Adverse effects of methylmercury: Environmental health research implications. *Environmental Health Perspectives* **118**(8), 1137–1145. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.0901757>
- Grigal, D. F. (2002). Inputs and outputs of mercury from terrestrial watersheds: A review. *Environmental Reviews* **10**(1), 1–39. <https://doi.org/10.1139/a01-013>
- Günther, F., Overduin, P. P., Sandakov, A. V., Grosse, G. & Grigoriev, M. N. (2013). Short- and long-term thermo-erosion of ice-rich permafrost coasts in the Laptev Sea region. *Biogeosciences* **10**(6), 4297–4318. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-10-4297-2013>
- Han, G., Ma, Z., Chen, N., Thomson, R. & Slangen, A. (2015). Changes in Mean Relative Sea Level around Canada in the Twentieth and Twenty-First Centuries. *Atmosphere - Ocean* **53**(5), 452–463. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07055900.2015.1057100>
- Harper, J. R. (1990). Morphology of the Canadian Beaufort Sea Coast. *Marine Geology* **91**, 75–91.
- Harrell, F. (2025). *Hmisc: Harrell Miscellaneous* (version 5.2-2) [Computer software]. https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=Hmisc*, last checked on 29. June 2025
- Hijmans, R. H. (2025). *terra: Spatial Data Analysis* (version 1.7-7.1) [Computer software]. https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=terra*, last checked on 29. June 2025
- Hill, P. R., Blasco, S. M., Harper, J. R. & Fissel, D. B. (1991). Sedimentation on the Canadian Beaufort Shelf. *Continental Shelf Research* **2**(10), 821–863.

- Hollweg, T. A., Gilmour, C. C. & Mason, R. P. (2010). Mercury and methylmercury cycling in sediments of the mid-Atlantic continental shelf and slope. *Limnology and Oceanography* **55**(6), 2703–2722. <https://doi.org/10.4319/LO.2010.55.6.2703>
- Holmes, R. M., McClelland, J. W., Peterson, B. J., Shiklomanov, I. A., Shiklomanov, A. I., Zhulidov, A. V., Gordeev, V. V. & Bobrovitskaya, N. N. (2002). A circumpolar perspective on fluvial sediment flux to the Arctic Ocean. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles* **16**(4), 45-1-45-14. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2001gb001849>
- Hong, Y. S., Kim, Y. M. & Lee, K. E. (2012). Methylmercury exposure and health effects. *Journal of Preventive Medicine and Public Health* **45**(6), 353–363. <https://doi.org/10.3961/jpmph.2012.45.6.353>
- Houde, M., Krümmel, E. M., Mustonen, T., Brammer, J., Brown, T. M., Chételat, J., Dahl, P. E., Dietz, R., Evans, M., Gamberg, M., Gauthier, M. J., Gérin-Lajoie, J., Hauptmann, A. L., Heath, J. P., Henri, D. A., Kirk, J., Laird, B., Lemire, M., Lennert, A. E., et al., Whiting, A. (2022). Contributions and perspectives of Indigenous Peoples to the study of mercury in the Arctic. *Science of the Total Environment* **841**, 156566. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2022.156566>
- Hugelius, G., Loisel, J., Chadburn, S., Jackson, R. B., Jones, M., Macdonald, G., Marushchak, M., Olefeldt, D., Packalen, M., Siewert, M. B., Treat, C., Turetsky, M., Voigt, C. & Yu, Z. (2020). Large stocks of peatland carbon and nitrogen are vulnerable to permafrost thaw. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **117**(34), 20438–20446. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1916387117/-/DCSupplemental>
- Hugelius, G., Strauss, J., Zubrzycki, S., Harden, J. W., Schuur, E. A. G., Ping, C. L., Schirmermeister, L., Grosse, G., Michaelson, G. J., Koven, C. D., O'Donnell, J. A., Elberling, B., Mishra, U., Camill, P., Yu, Z., Palmtag, J. & Kuhry, P. (2014). Estimated stocks of circumpolar permafrost carbon with quantified uncertainty ranges and identified data gaps. *Biogeosciences* **11**(23), 6573–6593. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-11-6573-2014>
- Inuvialuit Final Agreement (IFA) (2005). Indian and Northern Affairs Canada.
- IPCC. (2022). Polar Regions. In H.-O. Pörtner, D. C. Roberts, V. Masson-Delmotte, P. Zhai, M. Tignor, E. Poloczanska, K. Mintenbeck, A. Alegría, M. Nicolai, A. Okem, J. Petzold, B. Rama & N. M. Weyer (eds.), *IPCC Special Report on the Ocean and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate* (203–320): Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.
- IPCC (2023). *Climate Change 2023: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. <https://doi.org/10.59327/IPCC/AR6-9789291691647>
- Irrgang, A. M., Bendixen, M., Farquharson, L. M., Baranskaya, A. V., Erikson, L. H., Gibbs, A. E., Ogorodov, S. A., Overduin, P. P., Lantuit, H., Grigoriev, M. N. & Jones, B. M. (2022). Drivers, dynamics and impacts of changing Arctic coasts. *Nature Reviews Earth and Environment* **3**(1), 39–54. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-021-00232-1>
- Irrgang, A. M., Lantuit, H., Gordon, R. R., Piskor, A. & Manson, G. K. (2019). Impacts of past and future coastal changes on the Yukon coast — threats for cultural sites, infrastructure, and travel routes. *Arctic Science* **5**(2), 107–126. <https://doi.org/10.1139/as-2017-0041>
- Irrgang, A. M., Lantuit, H., Manson, G. K., Günther, F., Grosse, G. & Overduin, P. P. (2018). Variability in Rates of Coastal Change Along the Yukon Coast, 1951 to 2015. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface* **123**(4), 779–800. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017JF004326>
- James, G., Witten, D., Hastie, T. & Tibshirani, R. (2013). *An Introduction to Statistical Learning* (Bd. 103). Springer New York. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-7138-7>
- Ji, X., Abakumov, E., Tomashunas, V., Polyakov, V. & Kouzov, S. (2020). Geochemical pollution of trace metals in permafrost-affected soil in the Russian Arctic marginal environment. *Environmental Geochemistry and Health* **42**(12), 4407–4429. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10653-020-00587-2>
- Jiskra, M., Sonke, J. E., Agnan, Y., Helmig, D. & Obrist, D. (2019). Insights from mercury stable isotopes on terrestrial-atmosphere exchange of Hg(0) in the Arctic tundra. *Biogeosciences* **16**(20), 4051–4064. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-16-4051-2019>

- Jones, M. K. W., Jones, B. M., Nitze, I., Gessner, M., Grosse, G., Bartsch, A. & Bull, D. (2025). Annual and sub-seasonal dynamics of a rapidly eroding permafrost coastline along the Beaufort Sea in northern Alaska. *Scientific Reports* **15**(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-04753-3>
- Jong, D., Bröder, L., Tanski, G., Fritz, M., Lantuit, H., Tesi, T., Haghypour, N., Eglinton, T. I. & Vonk, J. E. (2020). Nearshore Zone Dynamics Determine Pathway of Organic Carbon From Eroding Permafrost Coasts. *Geophysical Research Letters* **47**(15), e2020GL088561. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GL088561>
- Jonsson, S., Mastromonaco, M. N., Wang, F., Bravo, A. G., Cairns, W. R. L., Chételat, J., Douglas, T. A., Lescord, G., Ukonmaanaho, L. & Heimbürger-Boavida, L. E. (2022). Arctic methylmercury cycling. *Science of the Total Environment* **850**, 157445. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2022.157445>
- Juhls, B., Matsuoka, A., Lizotte, M., Bécu, G., Overduin, P. P., Kassar, J. E., Devred, E., Doxaran, D., Ferland, J., Forget, M. H., Hilborn, A., Hieronymi, M., Leymarie, E., Maury, J., Oziel, L., Tisserand, L., Anikina, D. O. J., Dillon, M. & Babin, M. (2022). Seasonal dynamics of dissolved organic matter in the Mackenzie Delta, Canadian Arctic waters: Implications for ocean colour remote sensing. *Remote Sensing of Environment* **283**, 113327. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2022.113327>
- Juma, G. A., Meunier, C. L., Herstoff, E. M., Irrgang, A. M., Fritz, M., Weber, C., Lantuit, H., Kirstein, I. V. & Boersma, M. (2025). Future Arctic: how will increasing coastal erosion shape nearshore planktonic food webs? *Limnology and Oceanography Letters* **10**(1), 5–17. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lol2.10446>
- Kirk, J. L., Lehnerr, I., Andersson, M., Braune, B. M., Chan, L., Dastoor, A. P., Durnford, D., Gleason, A. L., Loseto, L. L., Steffen, A. & St. Louis, V. L. (2012). Mercury in Arctic marine ecosystems: Sources, pathways and exposure. *Environmental Research* **119**, 64–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2012.08.012>
- Kursa, M. B. & Rudnicki, W. R. (2010). Feature Selection with the Boruta Package. *Journal of Statistical Software* **36**(11), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v036.i11>
- Kwasigroch, U., Beldowska, M., Jędruch, A. & Saniewska, D. (2018). Coastal erosion—a “new” land-based source of labile mercury to the marine environment. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* **25**(28), 28682–28694. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11356-018-2856-7/FIGURES/4>
- Lamb, A. L., Wilson, G. P. & Leng, M. J. (2006). A review of coastal palaeoclimate and relative sea-level reconstructions using $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and C/N ratios in organic material. *Earth-Science Reviews* **75**(1-4), 29–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2005.10.003>
- Lantuit, H., Overduin, P. P., Couture, N. J., Wetterich, S., Aré, F., Atkinson, D., Brown, J., Cherkashov, G., Drozdov, D., Forbes, L. D., Graves-Gaylord, A., Grigoriev, M., Hubberten, H. W., Jordan, J., Jorgenson, T., Ødegård, R. S., Ogorodov, S., Pollard, W. H., Rachold, V., et al., Vasiliev, A. (2012). The Arctic Coastal Dynamics Database: A New Classification Scheme and Statistics on Arctic Permafrost Coastlines. *Estuaries and Coasts* **35**(2), 383–400. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12237-010-9362-6>
- Lantuit, H. & Pollard, W. H. (2005). Temporal stereophotogrammetric analysis of retrogressive thaw slumps on Herschel Island, Yukon Territory. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences* **5**, 413–423. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-5-413-2005>
- Lantuit, H. & Pollard, W. H. (2008). Fifty years of coastal erosion and retrogressive thaw slump activity on Herschel Island, southern Beaufort Sea, Yukon Territory, Canada. *Geomorphology* **95**(1-2), 84–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GEOMORPH.2006.07.040>
- Lehnerr, I. (2014). Methylmercury biogeochemistry: A review with special reference to Arctic aquatic ecosystems. *Environmental Reviews* **22**(3), 229–243. <https://doi.org/10.1139/er-2013-0059>
- Lehnerr, I., St. Louis, V. L., Hintelmann, H. & Kirk, J. L. (2011). Methylation of inorganic mercury in polar marine waters. *Nature Geoscience* **4**(5), 298–302. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo1134>
- Lehnerr, I., St. Louis, V. L. & Kirk, J. L. (2012). Methylmercury cycling in high arctic wetland ponds: Controls on sedimentary production. *Environmental Science and Technology* **46**(19), 10523–10531. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es300577e>
- Leitch, D. R. (2006). *Mercury distribution in water and permafrost of the lower Mackenzie Basin, their contribution to the mercury contamination in the Beaufort Sea marine ecosystem, and potential effects of climate variation* [Master's thesis]. University of Manitoba, Canada.

- Lemenkova, P. (2020). Mapping Beaufort Sea Topography and Geophysical Settings Using High-Resolution Geospatial Data and GMT. *Geographical Information* **24**(1), 4–18. <https://doi.org/10.17846/GI.2020.24.1.4-18>
- Liao, L., Selim, H. M. & Delaune, R. D. (2009). Mercury Adsorption-Desorption and Transport in Soils. *Journal of Environmental Quality* **38**(4), 1608–1616. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2008.0343>
- Liew, M., Xiao, M., Farquharson, L., Nicolsky, D., Jensen, A., Romanovsky, V., Peirce, J., Alessa, L., McComb, C., Zhang, X. & Jones, B. (2022). Understanding Effects of Permafrost Degradation and Coastal Erosion on Civil Infrastructure in Arctic Coastal Villages: A Community Survey and Knowledge Co-Production. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering* **10**(3), 422. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse10030422>
- Lim, A. G., Jiskra, M., Sonke, J. E., Loiko, S. V., Kosykh, N. & Pokrovsky, O. S. (2020). A revised pan-Arctic permafrost soil Hg pool based on Western Siberian peat Hg and carbon observations. *Biogeosciences* **17**(12), 3083–3097. <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-17-3083-2020>
- Lindqvist, O. & Rodhe, H. (1985). Atmospheric mercury—a review. *Tellus B* **37 B**(3), 136–159. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0889.1985.tb00062.x>
- Liu, Y., Chai, X., Hao, Y., Gao, X., Lu, Z., Zhao, Y., Zhang, J. & Cai, M. (2015). Total mercury and methylmercury distributions in surface sediments from Kongsfjorden, Svalbard, Norwegian Arctic. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* **22**(11), 8603–8610. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-014-3942-0>
- Loseto, L. L., Stern, G. A., Deibel, D., Connelly, T. L., Prokopowicz, A., Lean, D. R. S., Fortier, L. & Ferguson, S. H. (2008). Linking mercury exposure to habitat and feeding behaviour in Beaufort Sea beluga whales. *Journal of Marine Systems* **74**(3-4), 1012–1024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2007.10.004>
- Mackay, J. R. (1959). Glacial ice-thrust features of the Yukon coast. *Geographical Bulletin* **13**, 5.
- Mahbub, K. R., Bahar, M. M., Megharaj, M. & Labbate, M. (2018). Are the existing guideline values adequate to protect soil health from inorganic mercury contamination? *Environment International* **117**. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2018.04.037>
- Malinauskaite, L., Cook, D., Davíðsdóttir, B., Ögmundardóttir, H. & Roman, J. (2019). Ecosystem services in the Arctic: a thematic review. *Ecosystem Services* **36**, 100898. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2019.100898>
- Manson, G. K., Couture, N. J. & James, T. S. (2019). *CanCoast 2.0: data and indices to describe the sensitivity of Canada's marine coasts to changing climate*. https://ostrnrcan-dostrnrcan.canada.ca/entities/publication/caff0f1b-6adb-4470-be2c-d4461cf29793*, last checked on 29. June 2025
- Manson, G. K. & Solomon, S. M. (2007). Past and future forcing of Beaufort Sea coastal change. *Atmosphere - Ocean* **45**(2), 107–122. <https://doi.org/10.3137/ao.450204>
- Manson, G. K., Solomon, S. M., Forbes, D. L., Atkinson, D. E. & Craymer, M. (2005). Spatial variability of factors influencing coastal change in the Western Canadian Arctic. *Geo-Marine Letters* **25**(2-3), 138–145. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00367-004-0195-9>
- Mason, R. P., Reinfelder, J. R. & Morel, F. M. M. (1995). Bioaccumulation of Mercury and Methylmercury. *Water, Air, and Soil Pollution* **80**, 915–921.
- McDonald, B. C. & Lewis, C. P. (1973). *Geomorphic and sedimentologic processes of rivers and coast, Yukon Coastal Plain*. Geological Survey of Canada, Environmental-Social Program Northern Pipelines.
- Meinshausen, N. (2024). *quantregForest: Quantile Regression Forests* (version 1.3-7.1) [Computer software].
- Mekonnen, Z. A., Riley, W. J., Berner, L. T., Bouskill, N. J., Torn, M. S., Iwahana, G., Breen, A. L., Myers-Smith, I. H., Criado, M. G., Liu, Y., Euskirchen, E. S., Goetz, S. J., Mack, M. C. & Grant, R. F. (2021). Arctic tundra shrubification: a review of mechanisms and impacts on ecosystem carbon balance. *Environmental Research Letters* **16**(5), 53001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abf28b>
- Miner, K. R., D'Andrilli, J., Mackelprang, R., Edwards, A., Malaska, M. J., Waldrop, M. P. & Miller, C. E. (2021). Emergent biogeochemical risks from Arctic permafrost degradation. *Nature Climate Change* **11**, 809–819. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-021-01162-y>

- Molnar, C., Bischl, B. & Casalicchio, G. (2018). iml: An R package for Interpretable Machine Learning. *Journal of Open Source Software* **3**(26), 786. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00786>
- Mu, C., Zhang, F., Chen, X., Ge, S., Mu, M., Jia, L., Wu, Q. & Zhang, T. (2019). Carbon and mercury export from the Arctic rivers and response to permafrost degradation. *Water Research* **161**, 54–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2019.05.082>
- Mulligan, R. P. & Perrie, W. (2019). Circulation and structure of the Mackenzie River plume in the coastal Arctic Ocean. *Continental Shelf Research* **177**, 59–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csr.2019.03.006>
- National Snow and Ice Data Center (2025). *Sea Ice Spatial Comparison Tool*. https://nsidc.org/sea-ice-today/sea-ice-tools/sea-ice-spatial-comparison-tool*, last checked on 29. June 2025
- Nesterova, N., Leibman, M., Kizyakov, A., Lantuit, H., Tarasevich, I., Nitze, I., Veremeeva, A. & Grosse, G. (2024). Review article: Retrogressive thaw slump characteristics and terminology. *The Cryosphere* **18**(10), 4787–4810. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-18-4787-2024>
- Nielsen, D. M., Pieper, P., Barkhordarian, A., Overduin, P., Ilyina, T., Brovkin, V., Baehr, J. & Dobrynin, M. (2022). Increase in Arctic coastal erosion and its sensitivity to warming in the twenty-first century. *Nature Climate Change* **12**(3), 263–270. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01281-0>
- Obrist, D., Agnan, Y., Jiskra, M., Olson, C. L., Colegrove, D. P., Hueber, J., Moore, C. W., Sonke, J. E. & Helmig, D. (2017). Tundra uptake of atmospheric elemental mercury drives Arctic mercury pollution. *Nature* **547**(7662), 201–204. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature22997>
- Obu, J., Lantuit, H., Grosse, G., Günther, F., Sachs, T., Helm, V. & Fritz, M. (2017). Coastal erosion and mass wasting along the Canadian Beaufort Sea based on annual airborne LiDAR elevation data. *Geomorphology* **293**, 331–346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2016.02.014>
- Obu, J., Westermann, S., Bartsch, A., Berdnikov, N., Christiansen, H. H., Dashtseren, A., Delaloye, R., Elberling, B., Etzelmüller, B., Kholodov, A., Khomutov, A., Kääh, A., Leibman, M. O., Lewkowicz, A. G., Panda, S. K., Romanovsky, V., Way, R. G., Westergaard-Nielsen, A., Wu, T., et al., Zou, D. (2019). Northern Hemisphere permafrost map based on TTOP modelling for 2000–2016 at 1 km² scale. *Earth-Science Reviews* **193**, 299–316. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2019.04.023>
- Ogle, D. H., Doll, J. C., Wheeler, A. P. & Dinno, A. (2025). *FSA: Simple Fisheries Stock Assessment Methods* (version 0.9.6) [Computer software].
- Olson, C., Jiskra, M., Biester, H., Chow, J. & Obrist, D. (2018). Mercury in Active-Layer Tundra Soils of Alaska: Concentrations, Pools, Origins, and Spatial Distribution. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles* **32**(7), 1058–1073. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2017GB005840>
- Outridge, P. M., MacDonald, R. W., Wang, F., Stern, G. A. & Dastoor, A. P. (2008). A mass balance inventory of mercury in the Arctic Ocean. *Environmental Chemistry* **5**(2), 89–111. <https://doi.org/10.1071/EN08002>
- Outridge, P. M., Mason, R. P., Wang, F., Guerrero, S. & Heimbürger-Boavida, L. E. (2018). Updated Global and Oceanic Mercury Budgets for the United Nations Global Mercury Assessment 2018. *Environmental Science and Technology* **52**(20), 11466–11477. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b01246>
- Overduin, P. P., Deimling, T. S. v., Miesner, F., Grigoriev, M. N., Ruppel, C., Vasiliev, A., Lantuit, H., Juhls, B. & Westermann, S. (2019). Submarine Permafrost Map in the Arctic Modeled Using 1-D Transient Heat Flux (SuPerMAP). *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* **124**(6), 3490–3507. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018JC014675>
- Pelletier, B. R. (1984). *Marine science atlas of the Beaufort Sea: sediments*. Energy, Mines and Resources Canada.
- Perryman, C. R., Wirsing, J., Bennett, K. A., Brennick, O., Perry, A. L., Williamson, N. & Ernakovich, J. G. (2020). Heavy metals in the Arctic: Distribution and enrichment of five metals in Alaskan soils. *PLoS ONE* **15**(6). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0233297>
- Petzold, P. (2024). *Exploring the Impact of Wind Forcing on Organic Carbon Pathways in the Nearshore Zone of Herschel Island-Qikiqtaruk, Canada* [Master's thesis]. University of Potsdam, Germany.
- Pickart, R. S. (2004). Shelfbreak circulation in the Alaskan Beaufort Sea: Mean structure and variability. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* **109**(4). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2003JC001912>

- R Core Team. (2025). *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing* (version 4.3.3) [Computer software]. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>*, last checked on 29. June 2025
- Radosavljevic, B., Lantuit, H., Knoblauch, C., Couture, N. J., Herzs Schuh, U. & Fritz, M. (2022). Arctic Nearshore Sediment Dynamics—An Example from Herschel Island—Qikiqtaruk, Canada. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering* **10**(11), 1589. <https://doi.org/10.3390/JMSE10111589/S1>
- Ramage, J. L., Irrgang, A. M., Herzs Schuh, U., Morgenstern, A., Couture, N. J. & Lantuit, H. (2017). Terrain controls on the occurrence of coastal retrogressive thaw slumps along the Yukon Coast, Canada. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface* **122**(9), 1619–1634. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017JF004231>
- Rampton, V. N. (1982). *Quaternary geology of the Yukon Coastal Plain*. Geological Survey of Canada. https://searchworks.stanford.edu/view/1079504*, last checked on 29. June 2025
- Rantanen, M., Karpechko, A. Y., Lipponen, A., Nordling, K., Hyvärinen, O., Ruosteenoja, K., Vihma, T. & Laaksonen, A. (2022). The Arctic has warmed nearly four times faster than the globe since 1979. *Communications Earth and Environment* **3**(1), 168. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-022-00498-3>
- Raynolds, M. & Walker, D. (2022). *Raster Circumpolar Arctic Vegetation Map*. Mendeley Data **V2**.
- Reyes, F. R. & Lougheed, V. L. (2015). Rapid nutrient release from permafrost thaw in arctic aquatic ecosystems. *Arctic, Antarctic, and Alpine Research* **47**(1), 35–48. <https://doi.org/10.1657/AAAR0013-099>
- Rivkina, E., Laurinavichius, K., McGrath, J., Tiedje, J., Shcherbakova, V. & Gilichinsky, D. (2004). Microbial life in permafrost. *Advances in Space Research* **33**(8), 1215–1221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2003.06.024>
- Rutkowski, C., Lenz, J., Lang, A., Wolter, J., Mothes, S., Reemtsma, T., Grosse, G., Ulrich, M., Fuchs, M., Schirrmeister, L., Fedorov, A., Grigoriev, M., Lantuit, H. & Strauss, J. (2021). Mercury in Sediment Core Samples From Deep Siberian Ice-Rich Permafrost. *Frontiers in Earth Science* **9**, 718153. <https://doi.org/10.3389/FEART.2021.718153/BIBTEX>
- Salonen, V. P. & Korkka-Niemi, K. (2007). Influence of parent sediments on the concentration of heavy metals in urban and suburban soils in Turku, Finland. *Applied Geochemistry* **22**(5), 906–918. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeochem.2007.02.003>
- Schartup, A. T., Balcom, P. H., Soerensen, A. L., Gosnell, K. J., Calder, R. S. D., Mason, R. P., Sunderland, E. M. & St. Louis, V. L. (2015). Freshwater discharges drive high levels of methylmercury in Arctic marine biota. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* **112**(38), 11789–11794. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1505541112>
- Schirrmeister, L., Oezen, D. & Geyh, M. A. (2002). ²³⁰Th/U dating of frozen peat, Bol'shoy Lyakhovskiy Island (northern Siberia). *Quaternary Research* **57**(2), 253–258. <https://doi.org/10.1006/qres.2001.2306>
- Schuster, P. F., Schaefer, K. M., Aiken, G. R., Antweiler, R. C., Dewild, J. F., Gryziec, J. D., Gusmeroli, A., Hugelius, G., Jafarov, E., Krabbenhoft, D. P., Liu, L., Herman-Mercer, N., Mu, C., Roth, D. A., Schaefer, T., Striegl, R. G., Wickland, K. P. & Zhang, T. (2018). Permafrost Stores a Globally Significant Amount of Mercury. *Geophysical Research Letters* **45**(3), 1463–1471. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017GL075571>
- Schuster, P. F., Striegl, R. G., Aiken, G. R., Krabbenhoft, D. P., Dewild, J. F., Butler, K., Kamark, B. & Dornblaser, M. (2011). Mercury export from the Yukon River Basin and potential response to a changing climate. *Environmental Science and Technology* **45**(21), 9262–9267. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es202068b>
- Schuur, E. A. G., McGuire, A. D., Schädel, C., Grosse, G., Harden, J. W., Hayes, D. J., Hugelius, G., Koven, C. D., Kuhry, P., Lawrence, D. M., Natali, S. M., Olefeldt, D., Romanovsky, V. E., Schaefer, K., Turetsky, M. R., Treat, C. C. & Vonk, J. E. (2015). Climate change and the permafrost carbon feedback. *Nature* **520**(7546), 171–179. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14338>
- Schwarzkopf, K. (2023). *Distribution and origin of organic matter in marine surface sediments on the Canadian Beaufort Shelf* [Master's Thesis]. University of Tübingen, Germany.
- Scudder, G. G. E. (1997). Environment of the Yukon. In H. V. Danks & J. A. Downes (eds.), *Insects of the Yukon* (13–57). Biological Survey of Canada (Terrestrial Arthropods).

- Seelen, E., van Liem-Nguyen, Wünsch, U., Baumann, Z., Mason, R., Skjellberg, U. & Björn, E. (2023). Dissolved organic matter thiol concentrations determine methylmercury bioavailability across the terrestrial-marine aquatic continuum. *Nature Communications* **14**(1), 6728. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-42463-4>
- Semiletov, I., Pipko, I., Gustafsson, Ö., Anderson, L. G., Sergienko, V., Pugach, S., Dudarev, O., Charkin, A., Gukov, A., Bröder, L., Andersson, A., Spivak, E. & Shakhova, N. (2016). Acidification of East Siberian Arctic Shelf waters through addition of freshwater and terrestrial carbon. *Nature Geoscience* **9**, 361–365. <https://doi.org/10.1038/NEGO2695>
- Siegel, S. M. & Siegel, B. Z. (1984). First estimate of annual mercury flux at the Kilauea main vent. *Nature* **309**, 146–147.
- Skjellberg, U. (2012). Chemical Speciation of Mercury in Soil and Sediment. In G. Liu, Y. Cai & N. J. O'Driscoll (eds.), *Environmental Chemistry and Toxicology of Mercury* (1. edition, 219–258). Wiley Online Books. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118146644.ch7>
- Skjellberg, U., Bloom, P. R., Qian, J., Lin, C. M. & Bleam, W. F. (2006). Complexation of mercury(II) in soil organic matter: EXAFS evidence for linear two-coordination with reduced sulfur groups. *Environmental Science and Technology* **40**(13), 4174–4180. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es0600577>
- St. Pierre, K. A., St. Louis, V. L., Kirk, J. L., Lehnher, I., Wang, S. & La Farge, C. (2015). Importance of open marine waters to the enrichment of total mercury and monomethylmercury in lichens in the canadian high arctic. *Environmental Science and Technology* **49**(10), 5930–5938. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5b00347>
- St. Pierre, K. A., Zolkos, S., Shakil, S., Tank, S. E., Louis, V. L. S. & Kokelj, S. V. (2018). Unprecedented Increases in Total and Methyl Mercury Concentrations Downstream of Retrogressive Thaw Slumps in the Western Canadian Arctic. *Environmental Science and Technology* **52**(24), 14099–14109. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b05348>
- Stein, R. & MacDonald, R. W. (2004). *The Organic Carbon Cycle in the Arctic Ocean*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-18912-8>
- Stern, G. A., MacDonald, R. W., Outridge, P. M., Wilson, S., Chételat, J., Cole, A., Hintelmann, H., Loseto, L. L., Steffen, A., Wang, F. & Zdanowicz, C. (2012). How does climate change influence arctic mercury? *Science of the Total Environment* **414**, 22–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCITOTENV.2011.10.039>
- Stroeve, J. C., Serreze, M. C., Holland, M. M., Kay, J. E., Malanik, J. & Barrett, A. P. (2012). The Arctic's rapidly shrinking sea ice cover: A research synthesis. *Climatic Change* **110**(3-4), 1005–1027. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-011-0101-1>
- Suleymanov, A., Suleymanov, R., Kulagin, A. & Yurkevich, M. (2023). Mercury Prediction in Urban Soils by Remote Sensing and Relief Data Using Machine Learning Techniques. *Remote Sensing* **15**(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs15123158>
- Tanski, G., Couture, N. J., Lantuit, H., Eulenburg, A. & Fritz, M. (2016). Eroding permafrost coasts release low amounts of dissolved organic carbon (DOC) from ground ice into the nearshore zone of the Arctic Ocean. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles* **30**(7), 1054–1068. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015GB005337>
- Tanski, G., Wagner, D., Knoblauch, C., Fritz, M., Sachs, T. & Lantuit, H. (2019). Rapid CO₂ Release From Eroding Permafrost in Seawater. *Geophysical Research Letters* **46**(20), 11244–11252. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019GL084303>
- Tape, K. E., Sturm, M. & Racine, C. (2006). The evidence for shrub expansion in Northern Alaska and the Pan-Arctic. *Global Change Biology* **12**(4), 686–702. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2006.01128.x>
- Tarbier, B., Hugelius, G., Sannel, A. B. K., Baptista-Salazar, C. & Jonsson, S. (2021). Permafrost Thaw Increases Methylmercury Formation in Subarctic Fennoscandia. *Environmental Science and Technology* **55**(10), 6710–6717. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c04108>
- Terhaar, J., Lauerwald, R., Regnier, P., Gruber, N. & Bopp, L. (2021). Around one third of current Arctic Ocean primary production sustained by rivers and coastal erosion. *Nature Communications* **12**(1), 169. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-20470-z>

- Timmermans, M.-L. & Toole, J. M. (2023). The Arctic Ocean's Beaufort Gyre. *Annual Reviews of Marine Science* **15**, 47. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-marine-032122->
- Travnikov, O. (2005). Contribution of the intercontinental atmospheric transport to mercury pollution in the Northern Hemisphere **39**, 7541–7548. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2005.07.066>
- Turner, C. K. & Lantz, T. C. (2018). Springtime in the Delta: the Socio-Cultural Importance of Muskrats to Gwich'in and Inuvialuit Trappers through Periods of Ecological and Socioeconomic Change. *Human Ecology* **46**(4), 601–611. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10745-018-0014-y>
- Ullrich, S. M., Tanton, T. W. & Abdrashitova, S. A. (2001). Mercury in the aquatic environment: A review of factors affecting methylation. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology* **31**(3), 241–293. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20016491089226>
- UNEP (2013). *Global Mercury Assessment 2013: Sources, Emissions, Releases and Environmental Transport*. UNEP Chemicals Branch.
- van Everdingen, R. O. (1976). Geocryological terminology. *Canadian Journal of Earth Sciences* **13**(6), 862–867. <https://doi.org/10.1139/e76-089>
- Varty, S., Lehnherr, I., St. Pierre, K. A., Kirk, J. & Wisniewski, V. (2021). Methylmercury Transport and Fate Shows Strong Seasonal and Spatial Variability along a High Arctic Freshwater Hydrologic Continuum. *Environmental Science and Technology* **55**(1), 331–340. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c05051>
- Vaysse, K. & Lagacherie, P. (2017). Using quantile regression forest to estimate uncertainty of digital soil mapping products. *Geoderma* **291**, 55–64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2016.12.017>
- Vonk, J. E., Fritz, M., Speetjens, N. J., Babin, M., Bartsch, A., Basso, L. S., Bröder, L., Göckede, M., Gustafsson, Ö., Hugelius, G., Irrgang, A. M., Juhls, B., Kuhn, M. A., Lantuit, H., Manizza, M., Martens, J., O'Regan, M., Suslova, A., Tank, S. E., et al., Zolkos, S. (2025). The land–ocean Arctic carbon cycle. *Nature Reviews Earth and Environment* **6**(2), 86–105. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-024-00627-w>
- Vorobyova, E., Soina, V., Gorlenko, M., Minkovskaya, N., Zalinova, N., Mamukelashvili, A., Gilichinsky, D., Rivkina, E. & Vishnivetskaya, T. (1997). The deep cold biosphere: facts and hypothesis. *FEMS Microbiology Reviews* **20**(3-4), 277–290. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-6976.1997.tb00314.x>
- Wagner, J., Martin, V., Speetjens, N. J., A'Campo, W., Durstewitz, L., Lodi, R., Fritz, M., Tanski, G., Vonk, J. E., Richter, A., Bartsch, A., Lantuit, H. & Hugelius, G. (2023). High resolution mapping shows differences in soil carbon and nitrogen stocks in areas of varying landscape history in Canadian lowland tundra. *Geoderma* **438**, 116652. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2023.116652>
- Wagner, J., Wolter, J., Ramage, J., Martin, V., Richter, A., Speetjens, N. J., Vonk, J. E., Lodi, R., Bartsch, A., Fritz, M., Lantuit, H. & Hugelius, G. (2025). Regional synthesis and mapping of soil organic carbon and nitrogen stocks at the Canadian Beaufort coast **PREPRINT**. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-1052>
- Watras, C. J., Backa, R. C., Halvorsena, S., Hudson', R. J. M., Morrisona, K. A. & Wente', S. P. (1998). Bioaccumulation of mercury in pelagic freshwater food webs. *The Science of the Total Environment* **219**, 183–208. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-9697\(98\)00228-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-9697(98)00228-9)
- Weege, S. (2016). *Climatic drivers of retrogressive thaw slump activity and resulting sediment and carbon release to the nearshore zone of Herschel Island, Yukon Territory, Canada* [Doctoral Thesis]. University of Potsdam, Germany.
- Wegner, C., Bennett, K. E., Vernal, A. d., Forwick, M., Fritz, M., Heikkilä, M., Łącka, M., Lantuit, H., Laska, M., Moskalik, M., O'Regan, M., Pawłowska, J., Promińska, A., Rachold, V., Vonk, J. E. & Werner, K. (2015). Variability in transport of terrigenous material on the shelves and the deep Arctic Ocean during the Holocene. *Polar Research* **34**(1). <https://doi.org/10.3402/polar.v34.24964>
- Welsh, S. L. & Rigby, J. K. (1971). Botanical and physiographic reconnaissance of Northern Yukon. *Brigham Young University Science Bulletin* **14**(2).
- Wen, J., Wu, Y., Li, X., Lu, Q., Luo, Y., Duan, Z. & Li, C. (2021). Migration characteristics of heavy metals in the weathering process of exposed argillaceous sandstone in a mercury-thallium mining area. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* **208**, 111751. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2020.111751>
- Western Arctic (Inuvialuit) Claims Settlement Act (1984). Indian Affairs and Northern Development Canada.

- Westerveld, L., Kurvits, T., Schoolmeester, T., Mulelid, O. B., Eckhoff, T. S., Overduin, P. P., Fritz, M., Lantuit, H., Alfthan, B., Sinisalo, A., Miesner, F., Viitanen, L. -K. & NUNATARYUK consortium (2023). *Arctic Permafrost Atlas*. GRID-Arendal. <https://doi.org/10.61523/KPJI4549>
- Wetterich, S., Kizyakov, A. I., Opel, T., Grotheer, H., Mollenhauer, G. & Fritz, M. (2023). Ground-ice origin and age on Herschel Island (Qikiqtaruk), Yukon, Canada. *Quaternary Science Advances* **10**, 100077. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.qsa.2023.100077>
- Wickham, H. (2016). *ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis* (version 3.5.0) [Computer software]. Springer-Verlag. <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org>*, last checked on 29. June 2025
- WMAC-NS (2019). *Herschel Island-Qikiqtaruk Territorial Park Management Plan 2019*. Wildlife Management Advisory Council–North Slope.
- Wolter, J., Lantuit, H., Fritz, M., Macias-Fauria, M., Myers-Smith, I. & Herzsuh, U. (2016). Vegetation composition and shrub extent on the Yukon coast, Canada, are strongly linked to ice-wedge polygon degradation. *Polar Research* **35**(2016). <https://doi.org/10.3402/polar.v35.27489>
- Xie, W., Yu, Q., Fang, W., Zhang, X., Geng, J., Tang, J., Jing, W., Liu, M., Ma, Z., Yang, J. & Bi, J. (2024). Data-driven approaches linking wastewater and source estimation hazardous waste for environmental management. *Nature Communications* **15**(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-49817-6>
- Xu, J., Kleja, D. B., Biester, H., Lagerkvist, A. & Kumpiene, J. (2014). Influence of particle size distribution, organic carbon, pH and chlorides on washing of mercury contaminated soil. *Chemosphere* **109**, 99–105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHEMOSPHERE.2014.02.058>
- Yang, D., Shi, X. & Marsh, P. (2015). Variability and extreme of Mackenzie River daily discharge during 1973-2011. *Quaternary International* **380-381**, 159–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2014.09.023>
- Yang, Z., Fang, W., Lu, X., Sheng, G. P., Graham, D. E., Liang, L., Wullschleger, S. D. & Gu, B. (2016). Warming increases methylmercury production in an Arctic soil. *Environmental Pollution* **214**, 504–509. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2016.04.069>
- Zhang, Y., Jacob, D. J., Dutkiewicz, S., Amos, H. M., Long, M. S. & Sunderland, E. M. (2015). Biogeochemical drivers of the fate of riverine mercury discharged to the global and Arctic oceans. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles* **29**(6), 854–864. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015GB005124>
- Zolkos, S., Krabbenhoft, D. P., Suslova, A., Tank, S. E., McClelland, J. W., Spencer, R. G. M., Shiklomanov, A., Zhulidov, A. V., Gurtovaya, T., Zimov, N., Zimov, S., Mutter, E. A., Kutny, L., Amos, E. & Holmes, R. M. (2020). Mercury Export from Arctic Great Rivers. *Environmental Science and Technology* **54**(7), 4140–4148. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b07145>

Appendix

The data used for this thesis and the R code of model predictions can be found in the following GitHub folder:

<https://github.com/kathijsp/master-thesis>

MeHg extraction

Figure 27: MeHg extraction with two separate layers of two liquid mixtures: a lower clear layer containing DCM and the extracted MeHg, and an upper greenish layer containing KBr and CuSO_4 . The sediment has settled at the bottom of the tube.

Thermokarst landforms at the Yukon coast

Figure 28: Ice-wedge polygons (A) and thermokarst lakes (B) at the Yukon mainland coast, and coastal erosion at cliffs of HIQ (C).

Figure 29: Slump D on HIQ.

Figure 30: Active layer detachments on HIQ.

Grain size distribution

Figure 31: Grain size distribution for all YC24 samples. Cores, headwall, mud pool, stabilized zone, and thaw stream samples were taken from Slump D. T7 samples come from an exposed bluff at the mainland coast. Beach and marine samples are from the transect in front of Slump D. Mostly, samples are sorted by depth. Detailed information about samples can be found on GitHub.

Acknowledgements

Writing this master's thesis would not have been possible without the great support of my supervisor Dr. Michal Fritz, who always found the time and energy to answer my questions and gave me the chance to make so many new experiences. I am very grateful to Dr. Anna Irrgang, who was immediately motivated to supervise this thesis, and for her constructive feedback. This research has received funding from the EU Horizon Europe project ILLUQ (grant agreement No. 101133587).

Writing this master's thesis has taught me a lot. A big thank you goes to the great and experienced expedition team of the YC24 expedition. Thank you for your help during field days, for your time to support me, and for all the little moments I will never forget. This project was completed on Inuvialuit lands in the Inuvialuit Settlement Region. A special thanks goes to Peter Archie, Richard Gordon, Gina Slevinsky, and Philip Elanik, and all the people who supported our work.

Writing this master's thesis allowed me to travel to the University of Stockholm to conduct MeHg measurements. I want to say Thank You to the group of Sofi Jonsson for their warm welcoming, in particular to Charlotte Haugk, Alyssa Azaroff, Sam Mwaniki Gaita, and Sofi Jonsson for your great support during my lab work. After long days in the lab, it was great to exchange all the new impressions with someone who was listening. Thanks, Kathi, for letting me stay in your lovely flat and for sharing so many wonderful experiences.

Writing this master's thesis made me spend many hours in the lab of AWI Potsdam, where I received great and invaluable support from Alena, Jonas, and Justin. Thank You so much for explaining all the workflows and answering my questions whenever they came up. I am also very grateful to Juliane Wolter for sharing her Hg measurements with me to extend my data set.

Writing this master's thesis was so much easier thanks to the support and love from my family and friends. The biggest Thank You goes to Monika and Jürgen for your endless support throughout the entire journey leading to this thesis. I am also extremely grateful to the COPER group, Pia, Kimmy, Regina, and Robert for deep and small talks, chocolate at the right time, and all the input and motivation you gave me.

Tools used in this thesis

R version 4.3.3	statistical analysis, modeling, graphics
QGIS version 3.24.1-Tisler	map figures
ChatGPT	text editing, assistance with R coding
Citavi	literature management
NotebookLM	literature management
Mendeley	literature management
Consensus	literature search

Selbstständigkeitserklärung

Hiermit versichere ich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit ohne Hilfe Dritter und ohne Zuhilfenahme anderer als der angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe. Die den benutzten Quellen wörtlich oder inhaltlich entnommenen Stellen sind als solche kenntlich gemacht.

Die „Richtlinie zur Sicherung guter wissenschaftlicher Praxis für Studierende an der Universität Potsdam (Plagiatsrichtlinie) - Vom 20. Oktober 2010“, (https://www.uni-potsdam.de/fileadmin/projects/ambek/Amtliche_Bekanntmachungen/2011/ambek-2011-01-037-039.pdf), zuletzt aufgerufen am 18.06.25), habe ich zur Kenntnis genommen.

Potsdam, 18.08.2025

K. Jaspers
